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APPLICATION-LEVEL SWARM-BASED ORCHESTRATION ACROSS THE CLOUD-TO-EDGE CONTINUUM

D4.1 System Design and Demonstrator Specification

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Abbreviations

Term	Meaning
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
VPN	Virtual Private Network
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IoT	Internet of Things
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
VM	Virtual Machine
AWS	Amazon Web Services
ML	Machine Learning
APP	Application
WAN	Wide Area Network
NB-IoT	Narrowband IoT
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
MOM	Message Oriented Middleware
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
NFS	Network File System
RAID	Redundant Array of Independent Disks
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
DT	Digital Twin

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the design of the Decentralised AI-driven Swarmchestrator System and the specification of the four Demonstrator applications. The design targets to realise decentralised, self-organizing orchestration mechanism within the Swarmchestrator project which adopts a swarm-based, application-centric approach to resource management across the dynamic and heterogeneous Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

Key achievements of the system design include:

- identification of the various subsystems and their roles in the Swarmchestrator system
- clarification of capabilities and functionalities of the different subsystems the Swarmchestrator system consists of
- designing the interfaces for each subsystems
- identification of the internal components for each subsystems
- specification of the deployment requirements for the components building up the different subsystems
- integration of the cooperating subsystems

The project has 4 demonstrators for validating the decentralised, self-organising orchestration mechanism. For this purpose, a detailed analysis of the demonstrators and their requirements as well as the design of the demonstrator applications have taken place recently.

Note that the video scene analytics platform (aimed to be deployed in the municipality of Trento by TRE and FBK) defined in the submitted proposal, has been replaced by a sound analytics demonstrator system (in the municipality of Koper, developed by InnoRenew, as of September 2024) due to legal issues, which change went through the official procedure via amendment, resulting in an accepted, updated grant agreement .

Key achievements of the demonstrator specification include:

- understanding the operation of demonstrator applications
- elaborating the methodology on collecting technical and non-technical requirements of the demonstrator applications
- designing business and technical requirements questionnaire
- careful evaluation of the requirements questionnaire
- identification of the requirements of the demonstrators
- system design of the demonstrators
- identification of the metrics for monitoring and scaling
- performing the prototyping in its early stage

The works introduced above forms the basis for implementing the decentralised, self-organizing orchestration and for implementing the four demonstrators in the second phase of the project.

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the results of two separate, but related tasks, such as System Design (T4.1) and Demonstrator Specification (T4.2).

The Swarmchestrate project [1] has the goal to design and develop a decentralised, swarm-based orchestrator which utilises AI-driven intelligence, decentralised knowledge management, trust and identification of resources over the cloud to edge continuum. The design of the Swarmchestrate system focuses on the integration aspects of the subsystems (required to implement the overall system) without going into the details of the internal operation for the individual subsystems and components representing the building blocks.

The project also incorporates four demonstrator applications (demonstrators, for short) with objectives: (1) validate the Swarmchestrate implementation and operation in real-life contexts, (2) understand the processes of application (APP) development, integration, deployment with respect to the Swarmchestrate framework and components and (3) provide continuous feedback to the development of the Swarmchestrate (core) system to be generally applicable also incorporate practical aspects as well.

In the first period of the project, points (2) and (3) were relevant and in focus. Swarmchestrate core system developers had to understand the goals and requirements of the demonstrator applications, in order to establish concepts and tools that fulfill such demands as well. On the other hand, demonstrator developers had to get familiar with Swarmchestrate concepts, design and application development principles and practices (e.g., containerization, metric monitoring mechanisms, scaling concepts and policies, formalisms for application definition) to build a “Swarmchestrate-compliant” applications that can leverage from automated, decentralised orchestration and optimization possibilities offered.

The structure of the document is as follows. Section 2 presents the demonstrator applications, including a high-level overview and the methodology to assess general requirements as well as the actual requirements collected. Section 3 then introduces system design of the overall Swarmchestrate system focusing on the integration aspects including the introduction of the overall/integrated system as well as the individual subsystems’ roles, interfaces, components and deployments. Next, the specifications for all four demonstrators including design, metrics and prototypes are covered by Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes the overall results. In Section 6, references are listed. We also added the original requirement questionnaire and the demonstrators’ answer as appendix in Section 7.

2. Demonstrator Requirements

In this section, we introduce the four demonstrator applications at a high level, their goals, the context, the environment and the infrastructure available, as well as the main components, their connections, potential external services, and the conceptual system architecture, which are as follows:

- Demonstrator1:** Wastewater Manhole Management in Athens Metropolitan Sewage Network
- Demonstrator2:** Bi-modal operation of parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices
- Demonstrator3:** Noise classification in municipality of Koper
- Demonstrator4:** A metaverse digital twin of a natural habitat

Implementation of demonstrators, beyond validating the Swarmchestrate concept in real-life applications, has an important role to provide feedback for the development of the Swarmchestrate core system (in concepts and chosen technologies). First, it was necessary to understand and collect the set of requirements, prerequisites of the demonstrators, which then assisted in creating the more detailed, technical demonstrator specifications (presented in Section 4). In the following subsections, we introduce the methodology of how the initial requirements were identified, collected and grouped in a systematic way (in Section 2.1) and what were the actual requirements of the individual demonstrators (Section 2.3).

2.1 Methodology

As a first step, regular (weekly) demonstrators meetings were organised to understand the demonstrator applications (main objectives, high-level architecture, hardware and software environment), and see the requirements of the demonstrators, which must be fulfilled by the Swarmchestrate framework to be able to deploy and orchestrate these applications.

In parallel, to collect the technical and non-technical requirements, we analysed several former, related projects (COLA [2], CloudiFacturing [3], DIGITbrain [4]) to exploit previous, existing practices and experiences. Since the scope of those projects were slightly different, an intensive selection, refinement and extension activity was required to adapt those methodologies in the Swarmchestrate context.

An expert, requirements collection specialist (from UoW) was employed to choose and work out the methodology for requirements collection. As a result, it was decided that the means of collection would be a questionnaire. Then, the corresponding list of questions, relevant points of interest are phrased and structured. This questionnaire was refined in multiple iterations: a first draft was designed in a small group of experts, which was then consulted with the demonstrators (with regard to clarity, relevance, completeness), followed by creating the final version in consensus (see Section 2.3 for more details).

Before going into the details and results of the demonstrators' requirements, in the following section, we introduce the demonstrator applications to clarify the goals, scope and context.

2.2 Demonstrator applications

This section introduces the four demonstrator applications. Note that the descriptions, conceptual architectures, system design presented in this section do not aim to show integration details with the Swarmchestr^{ate} system, but focus merely (yet) on high-level goals and the application context.

2.2.1 Demonstrator 1: Wastewater Manhole Management in Athens Metropolitan Sewage Network

Due to climate change, Attica, the area including Athens and Piraeus City, has been affected by sudden and disastrous rainfalls, resulting in surface floods attributed to low-capacity sewage networks. The current measures, such as deploying mobile tankers, have been ineffective.

A viable solution is preventive monitoring of the network when heavy rainfall is predicted. Piraeus municipality will install sensors in 425 positions to monitor water flow levels, aiming to prevent flooding by identifying blockages and providing early warnings. In the case of extreme rainfall, authorities have only minutes to react, requiring sensors to measure and transmit data frequently. However, this would deplete the batteries of the devices, which are battery-operated.

The Swarmchestr^{ate} demonstrator aims to design an application that dynamically configures the sensors' operation, optimizing measurement and connection intervals based on external data sources, such as weather forecasting services. This will allow for the maximization of battery life without jeopardizing real-time flood detection alerts. By leveraging the Swarmchestr^{ate} cloud-to-edge continuum orchestration capabilities, the battery life of the deployed sensors is expected to exceed 5 years, providing detailed level measurements and real-time notifications during extreme rainfall events. Additionally, the application can scale from hundreds to thousands of devices in dispersed geographical areas.

The architecture of the demonstrator is illustrated in Figure 1 where we can see the difference of the measurement frequency depending on the weather conditions.

Figure 1 Demonstrator 1 conceptual system architecture

2.2.2 Demonstrator 2: Bi-modal operation of parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices

Urbanization and lack of efficient public transport infrastructure have led to the extensive use of public space for vehicle parking, prompting municipalities to deploy zoning systems to balance citizens' and businesses' needs. However, monitoring and managing these zones is challenging, and authorities often struggle to enforce proper use, resulting in poor experiences and economic losses.

To address this, municipalities deploy parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices, which provide real-time views of occupancy status and alert authorities to violations. These devices are battery-operated and use WAN networks, such as NB-IoT, to transmit data. However, the primary factor affecting operational cost is battery life, and most energy consumption is spent on WAN data transmission.

The Swarmchestrat demonstrator aims to optimize battery usage by automating the re-configuration of parking space devices to alternate between NB-IoT/push and BLE/poll modes based on expected connection frequency. When connection frequency is high, devices will switch to BLE/poll, and when low, they will switch to NB-IoT/push. This will maximize battery life without jeopardizing real-time identification of parking events, with an expected battery life exceeding 5 years. The application can also scale to thousands of devices in dispersed geographical areas, supporting different parking zone configuration requirements.

Figure 2 Demonstrator 2 conceptual system architecture

The architecture of the demonstrator is illustrated in Figure 2 where we can see how the data transmission technology is modified.

2.2.3 Demonstrator 3: Noise classification in municipality of Koper

The Municipality of Koper, a coastal city with both residential and touristic functions, faces growing urban noise due to traffic, tourism, and public events. These rising noise levels affect residents' quality of life and the urban soundscape. To address this, the city seeks IT-driven solutions that support real-time, data-informed urban planning while respecting citizen privacy. A key challenge is the need to classify noise sources as close as possible to the data source, avoiding centralized audio processing in the cloud, which raises concerns about privacy and system scalability.

Figure 3 Conceptual architecture of the noise source classification system

The proposed system (see Figure 3) consists of multiple edge devices and a remote server for data storage and visualization. Each edge device includes a Raspberry Pi, a sound level meter, and a microphone. The devices monitor noise levels and, when a predefined threshold is exceeded, capture a short audio clip for classification. To optimize quality of service, audio can be forwarded to nearby nodes—balancing the computational load, based on real-time device constraints, and keeping the raw audio in the edge network. Classification results and sound pressure level measurements are stored on the server and visualized through a monitoring dashboard.

As the system operates on a distributed network of edge devices deployed on public infrastructure, it must account for varying environmental conditions—especially differences in sunlight exposure that can raise device temperatures. Combined with the high CPU load required for audio classification, this can lead to thermal throttling and reduced performance. Swarmchestrat addresses this need by orchestrating containerized classification services in a decentralized manner, allowing the system to adapt to real-time changes in device status such as temperature and processing load. This ensures consistent performance while preserving privacy and supporting edge-based scalability.

2.2.4 Demonstrator 4: A metaverse digital twin of a natural habitat

UST is building a digital Twin of a natural system. This Digital Twin is delivered through an interactive map within a browser-based application, designed to visually represent the natural system under observation. This interface integrates data from a network of edge devices deployed throughout the area, each capturing real-time measurements of diverse environmental attributes (see Figure 4). Users can easily locate each device and understand

its role within the monitoring framework, gaining a holistic perspective of the system in place.

Figure 4 Conceptual architecture designed to observe the natural system

The platform allows users to explore both historical and live data by selecting specific time intervals. This functionality enables the identification of trends, patterns, and anomalies in environmental conditions over time. By interacting with the map and accessing detailed visualizations, researchers can strengthen their analyses and draw well-informed insights into the system's dynamics. The solution serves as a comprehensive tool that supports data-driven environmental studies by combining spatial context, temporal depth, and scientific detail into a single cohesive environment.

Swarmchestrat will play a key role in improving how edge devices are deployed and maintained across the environment. It will enable these devices to run for extended periods with reduced need for manual intervention, increasing operational efficiency. This will make it possible to build a more advanced and resilient digital twin, even in locations facing constraints such as limited connectivity, energy scarcity, shared resource usage, multiple simultaneous users, and irregular energy availability.

2.3 Business and technical requirements

The questionnaire to assess business and technical requirements of applications is discussed in this section. The questionnaires that had been filled out by the demonstrators are reported in the next section in detail. The questionnaire can be found in Appendix 7.1 to

save space; this section presents how the questions were grouped and what aspects were investigated.

The questionnaire was structured as follows: After a short introduction of the company/organization, the use case is presented at a conceptual level. It is followed by the estimation of the cost (or effort) needed to adapt the system to the Swarmchestrate environment, which are contrasted to the expected benefits of using Swarmchestrate. It can be important to see how users will use the application (because of the required interfaces to be provided), and the planned business model (in the case of commercial applications).

The introductory part is followed by the actual technical requirements, organised into sections: software, system (hardware, OS, virtualisation, etc.), data, performance and security requirements, in which specific elements, demands, constraints and further prerequisites can be enumerated if needed. The technical requirements section also contains a subsection to specify the financial requirements (if any), use of external services (which might be commercial), and a section to include further requirements not addressed by the preceding sections (Other requirements).

It is important to note that the questionnaire aimed not merely to address the particular technical demands of the actual four demonstrators but meant to be more general to cover potential new candidates willing to exploit Swarchestrate benefits. For this reason, it can happen that some of the questions were irrelevant in some use cases (giving answer: N/A).

The developed questionnaire that is to be filled out by application owners in order to assess requirements contains sections and questions (and hints) without particular answers (also called as “questionnaire template” because of empty spaces for answers).

2.4 Demonstrators’ requirements specifications

The business and technical requirements questionnaire that had been filled out by each demonstrator are presented in this section.

As noted earlier, these requirements had an impact on the design and implementation of the Swarchestrate system. For example, the use of external weather service affected the monitoring system (must allow of integrating custom monitoring probes), some sensors has temporal connectivity with the system, e.g. for some milliseconds four times a day (the orchestrator cannot assume permanent connection), there are special requirements to operate differently depending on the time of the day, e.g. in the case of solar-powered devices (triggering special events at certain times), or required code migration due to overheating by the sunshine (another custom monitoring event), respectively.

We note that to avoid duplications, some parts of the filled questionnaires are left out here to save space (e.g. Fuelics company description is the same for the two demonstrators) but keeping all the relevant information.

2.4.1 Demonstrator 1 requirements

Demonstrator/1

fuelics wastewater manhole management in Athens metropolitan sewage network

Company

Company Overview

Incorporated in 2019, Fuelics aimed to develop the first ever battery-operated NB-IoT exponential fuel management sensor for stationary diesel tanks. Our first prototype was realized in the early days of NB-IoT and monitored the fuel usage of a base station's stationary tank in a remote location.

Since then, our product portfolio has expanded exponentially and currently includes NB-IoT battery operated sensors for applications in diesel tank monitoring and delivery optimization, water and waste water tank management, septic tank and manhole overflow advance warning, roadside parking and anti-parking including accessible and EV charging spaces and data loggers for a wide range of smart meters.

Along with our partners and customers, we have embarked ourselves in a digital transformation journey transitioning from a hardware only manufacturing company to an end-to-end IoT solution provider, building in addition to hardware, in-house software and native mobile applications.

Our API-first design philosophy allows the seamless integration of our products with external platforms and services enabling our partners and customers to provide cutting edge end-to-end solutions tailor-made for the specific needs of each project.

Provide an overview, including its product/service, size, industry, main areas of operation, and so on.

- IoT hardware and software providers
- 10 employees
- Smart Cities, Oil & Gas

Core Competencies & Expertise

- IoT
 - Battery operated, constraint edge IoT devices
 - NB-IoT communication protocol
- Software development
 - Agile methodologies
 - TDD
 - CI/CD
 - Microservices architecture

- API design
 - REST
 - MQTT
- Cloud native design, deployment and operations
 - Containerization
- UI/UX
 - Web applications
 - Mobile applications

Fuelics technology stack allows remote management of battery operated sensors acting as sleeping nodes. The technology developed allows remote management on operational and hardware specification characteristics of any deployed sensors, allowing tailor-made adaptive reconfiguration of sensor profile to any emerging deployed need.

Clients (if applicable)

- Smart Cities
- Municipalities
- Oil & Gas

Are there specific application domains relevant to this project?

- Smart City IoT Platforms

Relevant Experience in Cloud & Edge Computing

Fuelics designs, develops and deploys battery operated NBIoT (Narrowband IoT) sensors for smart-city applications. The sensors are designed to operate as sleeping nodes, i.e. they are not permanently online and only connect to transmit data as infrequently as possible. The core capability of the sensors is to enable this behaviour in the bare-metal firmware that is deployed on each sensor's microcontroller and programmed to execute rule-based logic at the edge, allowing it to connect to the network either at scheduled intervals or when an event needs to be reported in real time. The sensors also support asynchronous remote-management which allows the modification of the rule-based logic, the schedule of connections and even low level-parameters of the sensors' electronics.

Fuelics has designed a wide variety of sensors with different capabilities, both in hardware and software, ranging from ultrasound based liquid level measuring sensors to magnetometer-based parking space occupancy sensors. Each sensor can be queried to report its hardware and software capabilities and configuration, as well as various operational parameters, such as network quality and battery capacity. The sensors are currently deployed in various locations all over Greece, as well as Europe and the Middle East.

In terms of cloud expertise, Fuelics has designed, deployed and operates the cloud infrastructure that allows data collection and remote management for IoT devices provided both by Fuelics as well as third party manufacturers. The cloud platform is cloud-provider

agnostic, it is fully containerized and can be deployed both in public cloud as well as hybrid and on-premises environments.

Last but not least, Fuelics designs, implements and provides a web based application and native mobile applications for Android and iOS devices.

Access to Cloud

Primarily Contabo (<https://contabo.com/en/>) an EU-owned global cloud infrastructure provider. Azure, Google GCP and AWS are also used in a case by case basis if explicitly requested by customers.

Motivation for Participating in this Demonstration

Fuelics sensors are industrialised TRL9 devices. The current proprietary technology stack allows manual remote management. In Swarmchestrator this manual management layer will be replaced by the Swarmchestrator orchestrator.

Type of Application

1. IoT
2. Web App/Service

Use Case Overview

Use Case Motivation and Objectives

Due to the climate change, Attica, the area that includes Athens and Piraeus City, two metropolitan cities hosting more than half of Greece's population, has been affected by sudden, very heavy and disastrous rainfalls. Their transitional behaviour accompanied with unprecedented volume of rain water results in disastrous surface floods attributed mainly to the low-capacity, imperfect, ill-maintained and poorly cleaned sewage networks.

In principle, water and sewage companies deploy anti-measures consisting of mobile tankers rushing towards the flooding sites trying to remedy the problem, but in vain. The only viable solution, since reconstructing an old sewage network is practically or financially impossible, is the preventive monitoring of the network when heavy rainfall is predicted.

Piraeus municipality has a very extensive piping network under a densely populated area. In 425 separate positions, under 80Kgr manhole lids, sensors will be installed by Fuelics in order to provide measurements from the lid level towards the bottom informing the Municipality about the water flow level. In Piraeus municipality the mandate is two-fold. Initially to prevent flooding by identifying the locations where debris, waste or tree leaves block the drainage and promptly clean them, therefore release water blockage and freely allowing water to be drained. Secondly, to provide early warning in real time in case of a flooding event.

In the case of an extreme rainfall, the time window the authorities have between detecting a possible flood event and reacting is in the order of minutes, which is the time it takes them

to deploy on-site anti-flood measures. This would require the deployed sensors to measure and transmit data very frequently. However, the deployed devices are battery operated and such a configuration would deplete the batteries after a few months of operation. The goal of this Swarmchestrate demonstrator is to design and develop an application that will monitor and dynamically configure the 425 sensors' operation by optimizing the measurement and connection interval of each sensor based on external data sources, such as weather forecasting services. This will allow the maximisation of the battery life without jeopardizing the real time flood detection alerts. By using the Swarmchestrate Cloud-to-Edge continuum orchestration capabilities, it is expected that the battery life of the deployed sensors will exceed the 5 year operational timespan while at the same time provide data during extreme rainfall events with detailed level measurements in the order of seconds and real time notifications to the authorities in case of an upcoming flooding event. An additional benefit of leveraging the Swarmchestrate orchestrator in this use case is that once the application is deployed, it can scale from hundreds to thousands of devices in widely dispersed geographical areas across cities or even countries.

Use Case High-level Architecture

Fig. 1. Use case high-level architecture

The conceptual system design is presented in the diagram above. The main components from left to right are as follows:

- **IoT devices** The Fuelics devices that are deployed in the manholes
- **IoT gateway** The software gateway that acts as the entry point for the bi-directional communication between the devices and the Fuelics IoT platform.
- **Fuelics IoT platform containers** There are two groups of containers
 - The purple coloured ones are the containers that provide the functionality of the IoT platform.

- The green/yellow/red ones are the containers that control the device reconfiguration. These are the containers that are actively managed by the Swarmchestrator orchestrator in order to adapt the devices' configuration to the expected weather conditions
- **Monitoring subsystem** The Swarmchestrator service that will convert the application level metrics to Service Level Agreements (SLOs) which will in turn trigger the application reconfiguration
- **Weather forecasting service** The external service that provides the forecast for the expected rainfall. The data from this service are converted to an application level metric by the Fuelics platform which is published to the monitoring service
- **Cloud Database/Messaging** The cloud based database/monitoring service used by the Fuelics platform

Current Users

- Municipality technical department
- IoT devices operators

If there are different user roles in the system, list them what features or services they can use (e.g., developer, system operator, system user).

The Fuelics platform supports role-based access to the IoT devices. The roles are:

- Viewer
- Editor
- Operator
- User manager
- Administrator

Deployment Process

The system components are packaged in Docker images. The deployment of the images is orchestrated with Docker Compose.

The deployment process is fully automated with just two manual steps that ensure system's stability and consistency. The development team implements the code changes in their local development environment where they can also verify that the changes work and have not affected existing functionality by running the automated test suites locally. The automated tests are split in unit, integration and system level tests. In order to prepare a new version of the deployment all code changes on any part of the platform must be pushed to the CI infrastructure where the same automated tests are executed in a clean environment. If all tests pass, the deployment artifacts are created.

The engineering team then triggers manually the creation of the docker images for each deployment that needs to be updated. Then, they ssh to the deployment VM, update the version of the docker images in the docker compose file and manually trigger the deployment update. These are the only manual steps of the deployment process.

User Interface

Fuelics platform provides a web application and native android and iOS applications.

Fig. 2. Web application screenshots

Fig. 3. Mobile application screenshots

Technologies, Platforms and Services Used

Cloud providers

- Contabo
- Azure

Programming languages

- Rust
- JavaScript

Proprietary software

- Fuelics cloud platform

External services

- Google Firebase
- Google Pub/Sub

Edge devices

- Fuelics IoT devices
 - Battery operated devices with a guaranteed operational period of 5 years
 - Network communication over NBloT
 - Remote management capabilities
 - “sleeping nodes” operation
 - Energy consumption for network connection and transmission is 10^2 to 10^3 higher compared to energy consumption for measurements.
 - The devices are in deep sleep most of the time to conserve power. They measure and connect based on their configuration. Measurement intervals can be in the order of seconds, connections in the order of minutes/hours/days in order to conserve energy.
 - Bare metal, in-house developed firmware
 - No support for applications that require an OS (e.g. docker)

Is the application cloudified & containerised?

Yes

Challenges or Limitations

The platform requires static IP addresses for:

1. IoT devices communication
2. External access to API and Web application

Swarmchestrator Use Case

Expected Benefits of using Swarmchestrator

The goal of the demonstrator is twofold. Firstly, to deploy an application that will dynamically reconfigure a large network of sensors (425 is expected to be installed), using data from external sources like weather forecast and weather statistics databases to

optimise the measurement and connection interval of each sensor, and maximise the battery life without decreasing the capability to detect a flood event.

The application will also use the external data to dynamically create Swarms of these application components (deployed as containerised microservices) in the Cloud-to-Edge continuum that will combine the measurements and use the upstream data to forecast a possible flood event before it actually occurs and gets detected by the physical sensor, thus providing Piraeus Municipality with a longer reaction window. The application will be able to use the sensor-containers to send reconfiguration commands to the sensors and physically change their behaviour as needed. Secondly, we will create large scale simulations of deployments, including hundreds to thousands of sensors in the Piraeus metropolitan area, using historical data of rainfall from previous years.

The aim is to validate the operation of the application in an even larger scale and assess the effectiveness of the deployments in a simulated environment which will allow authorities to have more confidence in selecting the proper location for the installation of the sensors before the actual rollout. This implementation will be utilising the decentralised simulation environment developed by Swarmchestr^{ate}.

What KPIs are expected to improve to what extent? What are the baseline values for these KPIs at the beginning of the Swarmchestr^{ate} project?

The primary KPI is the switch from manual to automatic devices reconfiguration.

Baseline: no automation

Goal: full automation

KPI_1: Fully automate the device reconfiguration process

An additional KPI can be defined in terms of the expected number of connections for each device. Currently, the devices are configured to connect at regular intervals in the order of hours. With the Swarmchestr^{ate} orchestration they will connect infrequently when the weather is good and more frequently when the weather is bad.

Taking into account an expected 20 days of heavy rainfall per year¹ we define the following KPI:

Baseline: 1 connection per hour => $365 \times 24 = 8760$ connections per year

Goal:

1 connection per day when the weather is good. 1 connection every 5 minutes when the expected rainfall is > 50mm. Assuming 20 days of heavy rainfall per year => $360 + 20 \times 24 \times 12 = 6120$ connections per year

Expected reduction of connections compared to baseline $(8760 - 6120)/8760 \sim 30\%$

KPI_2: Reduce the actual number of connections by 30%

¹ Kotroni, V., Bezes, A., Dafis, S., Founda, D., Galanaki, E., Giannaros, C., Giannaros, T., Karagiannidis, A., Koletsis, I., Kyros, G., Lagouvardos, K., Papagiannaki, K., & Papavasileiou, G. (2025). Long-Term Statistical Analysis of Severe Weather and Climate Events in Greece. *Atmosphere*, 16(1), 105. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos16010105>

The reduction of the expected connections per year will increase the expected lifetime of the devices. Currently, each device is designed to support 50500 connections with a single battery pack which leads to an expected lifetime of $50500 / 8760 \sim 5.7$ years.

With the optimized device configuration the expected lifetime is $50500 / 6120 \sim 8.25$ years. This is an improvement of $(8.25 - 5.7)/5.7 \sim 45\%$

KPI_3: Increase the expected lifetime of the devices by 45%

In order to capture more fine-grained information for average rainfall cases, we will define three configuration profiles for expected rainfall in the range of >30mm, >40mm and >50mm. We can capture this with the following KPI

KPI_4: Define 3 distinct profiles for different expected rainfall levels

Required Adaptation Efforts

- Implement application level metrics prometheus/open-telemetry providers
- Implement device re-configurator services
- Adapt the Fuelics platform application description from docker compose to TOSCA² compliant format

Enumerate the list of “users” of the system, which may include developers and testers (who develop container images/application descriptors) of the application, operator (who deploys and monitors), end users (who use the application).

1. Software architect
2. Software developers
3. Operations engineer

For each user, specify what they will do, and what competencies are needed (e.g. programming/orchestration concepts/Swarmchestrator system/Kubernetes, domain competence).

1. Software architect
Conceptualize, design and document the new system software architecture
2. Software developers
Implement the required changes
3. Operations engineer
Deploy and monitor the new system’s operational

² <https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML/v1.3/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML-v1.3.html>

Business Model(s)

Fuelics combines state of the art edge computing battery operated sensors with a cloud agnostic Internet of Things (IoT) platform to offer real time measurements of waste and rainwater underground levels. The provided service aims at Smart Municipalities that usually procure large scale sensor projects, where the contract is paid to deliver hardware and software for at least 2 years after the delivery of the project.

Fuelics offers the monitoring service as a SaaS with or without the hardware cost being amortized over the SaaS fee.

When the 425 radar sensor pilot is deployed in Piraeus municipality (Q3 of 2025), Swarmchestrate will optimize the sensor usage based on weather forecasting. As a tool, municipal staff will be able to rapidly identify occurrences that require their attention.

Fuelics Business model. Offer sensors to be installed under pits for wastewater and rainwater level measurement and a SaaS platform and native mobile App for monitoring. The expected benefit of Swarmchestrate in terms of the business model is to scale the device configuration capability from 10^1 to 10^4 devices and at the same time improve the data quality and the battery life expectancy.

At the moment it cannot be measured if this improvement will outweigh the cost of running the Swarmchestrate infrastructure. If yes, then this may lead to a different business model for the Fuelics solution offering.

Is it commercial/open-source development?

Commercial

Will Swarmchestrate change the business model e.g. pricing model, customer/user engagement, or service delivery?

Yes

The business model briefly (pay-per-use, contract for a period, customer).

Contract for a period

Use Case Requirements

Software Requirements

Enumerate the list of software used by the use case (OS, open source, proprietary software, licences, databases, own developments etc.).

- Linux/debian based
- docker

- Fuelics IoT platform (own development)
- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)
- Google GCP Pub/Sub (SaaS Message Oriented Middleware (MoM))

System Requirements

Enumerate hardware (hosts, RAM, CPU, ...) environment(s) required to operate the system.

- ~ 1Gb RAM
- 2 vCPUs

Indicate preferred clouds (if used).

- Contabo

Enumerate use case-specific devices (e.g., edge devices, sensors, connectivity option).

- Fuelics radar NB IoT devices

Data Requirements

Enumerate databases, file storages (cloud storages, etc.) required by the system.

- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)
- Google GCP Pub/Sub (SaaS Message Oriented Middleware (MoM))

Estimate the amount of data produced/processed/exchanged (if applicable).

- < 1MB/day for a few hundred devices

Describe briefly where/how these will be stored (maintained, replicated, backed up, ...).

- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)

Do you already have cloud storage in a public cloud provider e.g. AWS, Azure, ...?

Yes, Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)

External Services

Describe if any external services will be used.

- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)
- Google GCP Pub/Sub (SaaS Message Oriented Middleware (MoM))

Performance Requirements

List the performance criteria required to ensure the minimum (normal) QoS goals (e.g., response times, network bandwidths, CPU speed).

- Response time < 5 secs for the communication between the platform and the device
- Network bandwidth > 100 Kbps
- CPU speed N/A

Financial Requirements

How important is cost efficiency/optimisation for the application?

Very important, especially in terms of the choice of cloud provider.

Are there specific cost constraints or considerations?

(e.g., restrictions on spending per workload, preference for certain cloud providers due to cost advantages, etc.)

- EU-owned based cloud providers
- Minimal cost of VMs

Security Requirements

Enumerate and explain the security requirements that must be fulfilled to safely operate the system (e.g., encryption, sensitive data, protection of access, VPN, etc.).

Nothing in addition to what is already provided by the Fuelics IoT platform.

QoS Requirements

Are there strict latency requirements?

Yes, response time for IoT devices communication < 5 secs

Energy Consumption Requirements

Are you required to use green/renewable energy for cloud & edge resources?

No

Do you have energy consumption constraints for Cloud & Edge Resources (e.g. kWh/application or kWh/month)?

Yes, the devices are battery operated. The energy consumed is measured by the number of connections per day. The goal is to optimize this and connect only when necessary.

Other Requirements

Are there specific geographical constraints for deployment? (e.g., due to data protection). Please specify the Continent, Country, City and GPS if applicable)

Cloud providers should be EU-owned companies

Are there any other requirements not fitting to the above categories)?

No

2.4.2 Demonstrator 2 requirements

Demonstrator/2

bi-modal operation of parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices

Use Case Overview

Use Case Motivation and Objectives

Urbanisation and high population density in modern cities combined with the lack of efficient public transport infrastructure has led to the extensive use of public space for vehicle parking purposes. In order to optimize the parking space occupancy, municipalities deploy zoning systems to balance the use of the public space between the citizens' and business's needs.

1. In areas with high parking demand, metered parking zones are defined where the citizens can park for a short amount of time, usually for a fee (e.g. commercial areas, public buildings, recreational areas etc.)
2. In order to support the logistical operations of businesses, designated loading and unloading areas are defined where short term parking is allowed for transport vehicles at specific times within the day, usually during off-peak hours.
3. In residential areas restricted parking zones are defined where only the local residents are allowed to park.
4. Especially for citizens with disabilities, designated parking spaces are allocated where the parking is allowed for special permit holders only.

The monitoring and management of these zones is increasingly difficult as the city size increases. The authorities do not have the capacity to patrol and enforce the proper use of

the designated parking zones which leads to poor experience for both citizens and businesses as well as economic loss in the case of metered parking spaces. In order to improve the efficiency of the monitoring of parking space occupancy, municipalities deploy parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices city wide. The purpose of the parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices is two fold:

1. Provide real-time view of the status of the occupancy for selected areas and alert in case the parking conditions are violated, e.g. overrun parking time, parking at a space without the proper permit etc. This allows the municipalities to use their patrolling teams more efficiently .
2. Collect occupancy data in order to adapt the zoning requirements as the citizens and business change the way they use public space.

Due to the large geographical area the parking space occupancy monitoring sensors are deployed, and in order to reduce the cost of their installation, the devices are battery operated and use WAN networks for transmitting the occupancy information. The reason battery operated devices are preferred is to avoid the additional cost of the public works required to connect these devices directly to the power grid. In terms of the WAN technology used, one of the most commonly used in NBloT which uses the mobile operators' cellular network and does not require the deployment of additional wireless network infrastructure. In order to support identification of parking events in spaces where a specific permit is required, the parking space devices support Bluetooth (BLE) and can detect proximity tags to identify if the vehicle is allowed to park or not. The BLE mode is also used during device commissioning and allows the field engineers to connect to the devices via their mobile phones, change their configuration and also retrieve the current occupancy status for testing purposes.

The primary factor that affects the operational cost of these devices is the battery life as the cost of replacing them can become prohibitively high when thousands of devices are deployed all over the city. In regards to the energy consumption of the devices, most of it is spent on the WAN data transmission. The parking space occupancy monitoring devices connect and transmit their data when a vehicle occupies or leaves a monitored parking space. The connection frequency cannot be known in advance and it is therefore not possible to predict how long the battery of the device will last. In terms of specifications, the common practice is to provide an estimate of the number of connections a device can support with a single battery pack. If the frequency of parking events is known, the device's expected operational time can be calculated.

The energy required to transmit a message over NBloT (WAN) in ideal conditions is ~15 times higher than the energy required to transmit a message over BLE (LAN), as we have established during measurements in our lab. This insight may lead us to a deployment strategy that can increase the life expectancy of parking space sensors.

Fig. 1. Conceptual architecture

The primary difference between NB-IoT and BLE is that the former has the adequate power to transmit information directly from the device to the cloud in a push fashion (hence the increased energy needs) whereas the latter requires a local gateway to poll the status of the device and take over the push of the information to the cloud. The wireless nature of BLE gives some limited flexibility on the placement of the local gateway which can be close to a power source thus not requiring to be itself battery operated.

The choice between these two operational modes is not clear-cut and may vary depending on the parking zone requirements as well as the time of day for each individual device. The primary metric to determine the optimal selection is the expected frequency of the parking events. In case the parking spaces are in a busy area and allow only for short-time parking (e.g. 10-15 minutes) the number of connections per hour will be high. Similarly, if the parking spaces are used for parking occupancy avoidance in busy areas, the connections can also be high due to vehicles occupying the space for a few minutes. This favours the use of a local BLE gateway operating in polling mode. On the other hand, outside of busy hours, during the night, or in residential parking zones, the parking events frequency will be low which favours the use of direct transmission via NB-IoT in push mode.

In an attempt to optimize the battery usage and maximize the operational lifetime of the parking space devices, this demonstrator will leverage the Swarmchestrator cloud-to-edge continuum orchestration capabilities to automate the re-configuration of the parking space devices and alternate their operational mode between NB-IoT/push and BLE/poll. When the connection frequency is expected to be high, the configuration will dynamically switch from Wide-Area communication technologies (NB-IoT) to the use of a Local-Area (BLE) gateway which has lower energy requirements for connection and data transmission. When the connection frequency is expected to be low, the opposite will happen and the configuration

will dynamically switch from Local-Area (BLE) to Wide-Area (NBloT) communication. This will allow the maximisation of the battery life without jeopardizing the real time identification of parking events. By leveraging the Swarmchestrate cloud-to-edge continuum orchestration capabilities, it is expected that the battery life of the deployed sensors will consistently exceed the 5 year operational timespan. An additional benefit of leveraging the Swarmchestrate orchestrator in this use case is that once the application is deployed, it can scale from hundreds to thousands of devices in widely dispersed geographical areas supporting different parking zone configuration requirements.

Use Case High-level Architecture

Fig. 2. Use case high-level architecture

The conceptual system design is presented in the diagram above. The main components from left to right are as follows:

- **IoT devices** The Fuelics parking space monitoring devices that are deployed.
- **IoT gateway** The software gateway that acts as the entry point for the bi-directional communication between the devices and the Fuelics IoT platform.
- **Fuelics IoT platform containers** There are two groups of containers
 - The purple coloured ones are the containers that provide the functionality of the IoT platform.
 - The green/blue ones are the containers that control the device reconfiguration. These are the containers that are actively managed by the Swarmchestrate orchestrator in order to alternate the devices' configuration between the two operational modes, WAN (MBIoT) and LAN (BLE).
- **Monitoring subsystem** The Swarmchestrate service that will convert the application level metrics to Service Level Agreements (SLOs) which will in turn trigger the application reconfiguration

- **Cloud Database/Messaging** The cloud based database/monitoring service used by the Fuelics platform

Current Users

- Municipality technical department
- IoT devices operators

If there are different user roles in the system, list them what features or services they can use (e.g., developer, system operator, system user).

The Fuelics platform supports role-based access to the IoT devices. The roles are:

- Viewer
- Editor
- Operator
- User manager
- Administrator

Deployment Process

The system components are packaged in docker images. The deployment of the images is orchestrated with Docker Compose.

The deployment process is fully automated with just two manual steps that ensure system's stability and consistency. The development team implements the code changes in their local development environment where they can also verify that the changes work and have not affected existing functionality by running the automated test suites locally. The automated tests are split in unit, integration and system level tests. In order to prepare a new version of the deployment all code changes on any part of the platform must be pushed to the CI infrastructure where the same automated tests are executed in a clean environment. If all tests pass, the deployment artifacts are created.

The engineering team then triggers manually the creation of the docker images for each deployment that needs to be updated. Then, they ssh to the deployment VM, update the version of the docker images in the docker compose file and manually trigger the deployment update. These are the only manual steps of the deployment process.

User Interface

Fuelics platform provides a web application and native android and iOS applications.

Fig. 3. Web application screenshots

Fig. 4. Mobile application screenshots

Technologies, Platforms and Services Used

Cloud providers

- Contabo
- Azure

Programming languages

- Rust
- JavaScript

Proprietary software

- Fuelics cloud platform

External services

- Google Firebase
- Google Pub/Sub

Edge devices

- Fuelics IoT devices
 - Battery operated devices with a guaranteed operational period of 5 years
 - Network communication over NBloT
 - Remote management capabilities
 - “sleeping nodes” operation
 - Energy consumption for network connection and transmission is 10^2 to 10^3 higher compared to energy consumption for measurements.
 - The devices are in deep sleep most of the time to conserve power. They measure and connect based on their configuration. Measurement intervals can be in the order of seconds, connections in the order of minutes/hours/days in order to conserve energy.
 - Bare metal, in-house developed firmware
 - No support for applications that require an OS (e.g. docker)

Is the application cloudified & containerised?

Yes

Challenges or Limitations

The platform requires static IP addresses for:

1. IoT devices communication
2. External access to API and Web application

Swarmchestrator Use Case

Expected Benefits of using Swarmchestrator

The demonstrator will leverage the Swarmchestrator to upgrade the parking space devices from single mode to multi-mode operation. The core idea is to use an edge device that has local connectivity with the deployed parking space devices and use Swarmchestrator to

alternate between WAN and LAN mode based on the expected parking space occupancy frequency. Swarmchestrate will be used to orchestrate the change of the operational mode from NBloT/push to BLE/pull by deploying appropriate containerized microservices to the edge devices that communicate with the parking spaces in order to retrieve the data using a local BLE connection and reconfigure them to use NBloT when BLE is no longer necessary. In order to trigger the deployment reconfiguration, application level metrics will be used that will be used by the Swarmchestrate monitoring component to calculate an SLO which will be linked via the TOSCA definition to the appropriate deployment configuration.

What KPIs are expected to improve to what extent? What are the baseline values for these KPIs at the beginning of the Swarmchestrate project?

The primary KPI is the switch from manual to automatic devices reconfiguration.

Baseline: no automation

Goal: full automation

KPI_1: Fully automate the device reconfiguration process

An additional KPI can be defined in terms of the expected life expectancy of a parking space device. Currently, the devices are configured to connect when a parking event occurs. With the Swarmchestrate orchestration the devices will alternate between push and poll modes which will reduce the number of WAN connections.

The Fuelics parking devices support 40.000 NBloT transmissions with a single battery pack. Assuming 11 parking events per day on average, the devices will connect 22 times every day (once for reporting the occupancy and once for the release of the parking space). With these assumptions, the expected device operational period is:

$$40.000 / 22 / 365 \sim 5 \text{ years}$$

In case the parking spaces are in a busy area and allow only for a short time parking, (e.g 10-15 minutes), the number of connections will be much higher than the previous assumption, about 12 per hour. Assuming a “busy” period of 6 hours, there will be more than 60 connections in this period, 3 times more than the assumed connections for a whole day.

The results from our internal lab measurements indicate that the energy requirements for retrieving the occupancy data over BLE is one order of magnitude lower compared to using NBloT. A short BLE Connection to fetch the necessary information (1-2s) would consume on average 15 times less energy than transmitting a typical NB-loT message under ideal network conditions. Continuing the example case, if BLE was used instead with a polling frequency of 1 min, the device would use 60 BLE messages per hour. A NBloT message “costs” 15 times more than a BLE message in terms of energy. Thus, NBloT compared to BLE would required

$$E_{\text{NBloT}}/E_{\text{BLE}} = (12*15) /60 = 3 \text{ times more energy in ideal conditions.}$$

The expected improvement of the daily energy consumption is:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{NBloT_only}}/E_{\text{BLE_ \& NBloT}} &= E_{\text{NBloT_only}}/[(E_{\text{BLE}} * 6 + E_{\text{NBloT_only}} * 18)/24] \\ &= E_{\text{NBloT_only}}/[(1/3 * E_{\text{NBloT_only}} * 6 + E_{\text{NBloT_only}} * 18)/24] \\ &= \\ 1/[(0.33 * 6 + 18)/24] &\sim 1.2 \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$E_{\text{NBloT_only}} = 1.2 * E_{\text{BLE_ \& NBloT}}$$

All other parameters being equal, in this example the expected life time of the device will increase by 20%, from 5 to 6 years. Of course, the improvement of the life expectancy depends heavily on the actual parking space occupancy frequency.

For evaluation purposes, we will compare parking space device deployed in the same area in order to have a similar parking occupancy profile. The KPI we will is the following:

KPI_2: improve the life expectancy of parking space devices by a minimum of 20%

Required Adaptation Efforts

- Design and construct a new BLE gateway that can run docker containers and is accessible to Swarmchestrate via 4G. The BLE gateway will be deployed in the vicinity of parking space devices
- Implement application level metrics prometheus/open-telemetry providers
- Implement device re-configurator services
- Adapt the Fuelics platform application description from docker compose to TOSCA compliant format

Enumerate the list of “users” of the system, which may include developers and testers (who develop container images/application descriptors) of the application, operator (who deploys and monitors), end users (who use the application).

1. Hardware engineer
2. Software architect
3. Software developers
4. Operations engineer

For each user, specify what they will do, and what competencies are needed (e.g. programming/orchestration concepts/Swarmchestrate system/Kubernetes, domain competence).

1. Hardware engineer
Conceptualize, design and construct the new BLE gateway
2. Software architect

- Conceptualize, design and document the new system software architecture
- 3. Software developers
Implement the required changes
- 4. Operations engineer
Deploy and monitor the new system's operational

Business Model(s)

Fuelics combines state of the art edge computing battery operated sensors with a cloud agnostic Internet of Things (IoT) platform to offer real time measurements of waste and rainwater underground levels. The provided service aims at Smart Municipalities that usually procure large-scale sensor projects, where the contract is paid to deliver hardware and software for at least 2 years after the delivery of the project.

Fuelics offers the monitoring service as a SaaS with or without the hardware cost being amortized over the SaaS fee.

When the BLE gateway is deployed, the parking space devices are expected to gain at least 20% lifetime, proportionally improving the operational cost of the deployment.

Fuelics Business model. Fuelics provides parking space devices to be installed in locations that the municipality wants to monitor. The expected benefit of Swarmchestrate in terms of the business model is to reduce the operational cost of the solution leading to a more competitive commercial offering.

At the moment it cannot be measured if this improvement will outweigh the cost of running the Swarmchestrate infrastructure. If yes, then this may lead to a different business model for the Fuelics solution offering.

Is it commercial/open-source development?

Commercial

Will Swarmchestrate change the business model e.g. pricing model, customer/user engagement, or service delivery?

Yes

The business model briefly (pay-per-use, contract for a period, customer).

Contract for a period

Use Case Requirements

Software Requirements

- Linux/debian based
- docker
- Fuelics IoT platform (own development)
- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)
- Google GCP Pub/Sub (SaaS Message Oriented Middleware (MoM))

System Requirements

Enumerate hardware (hosts, RAM, CPU, ...) environment(s) required to operate the system.

- ~ 1Gb RAM
- 2 vCPUs

Indicate preferred clouds (if used).

- Contabo

Enumerate use case-specific devices (e.g., edge devices, sensors, connectivity option).

- Fuelics radar NB IoT devices

Data Requirements

- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)
- Google GCP Pub/Sub (SaaS Message Oriented Middleware (MoM))

Estimate the amount of data produced/processed/exchanged (if applicable).

- < 1MB/day for a few hundred devices

Describe briefly where/how these will be stored (maintained, replicated, backed up, ...).

- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)

Do you already have cloud storage in a public cloud provider e.g. AWS, Azure, ..?

Yes, Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)

External Services

- Google GCP firebase (SaaS database)
- Google GCP Pub/Sub (SaaS Message Oriented Middleware (MoM))

Performance Requirements

- Response time < 5 secs for the communication between the platform and the device
- Network bandwidth > 100 Kbps
- CPU speed N/A

Financial Requirements

How important is cost efficiency/optimisation for the application?

Very important, especially in terms of the choice of cloud provider.

Are there specific cost constraints or considerations?

(e.g., restrictions on spending per workload, preference for certain cloud providers due to cost advantages, etc.)

- EU-owned based cloud providers
- Minimal cost of VMs

Security Requirements

Nothing in addition to what is already provided by the Fuelics IoT platform.

QoS Requirements

Response time for IoT devices communication < 5 secs

Energy Consumption Requirements

Do you have energy consumption constraints for Cloud & Edge Resources (e.g. kWh/application or kWh/month)?

The devices are battery operated. The energy consumed is measured by the number of connections per day. The goal is to optimize this and connect only when necessary.

Other Requirements

Are there specific geographical constraints for deployment? (e.g., due to data protection).

Please specify the Continent, Country, City and GPS if applicable)

Cloud providers should be EU-owned companies

Are there any other requirements not fitting to the above categories)?

No

2.4.3 Demonstrator 3 requirements

InnoRenew CoE

Company Overview

InnoRenew CoE is an independent research institute established in 2017, dedicated to advancing renewable materials and sustainable construction practices. The institute brings together a multidisciplinary team to conduct applied research, with a strong emphasis on

transferring scientific discoveries into industrial and societal impact. InnoRenew CoE operates from its own headquarters—the largest wooden building in Slovenia—where a comprehensive Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) system continuously gathers real-time data using load cells, accelerometers, VOC/CO₂ sensors, and multi-depth wood moisture content sensors to evaluate building performance and material behavior.

InnoRenew CoE excels in the design and deployment of both wired and wireless sensor networks, offering end-to-end services from custom sensor integration to platform management. Its Information Processing Research Department has developed scalable and extensible solutions for Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) monitoring, large-scale wireless network management, and on-sensor data processing. These systems support real-time and historical data analysis, threshold-based alerts, and remote updates, making them suitable for smart building applications. The institute's expertise also extends to developing distributed computing architectures and privacy-preserving protocols for data collection and edge processing. InnoRenew CoE is actively engaged in research and development of cutting-edge technologies such as digital product passports, blockchain-based traceability systems, and AI-augmented decision support tools. With proven capabilities in graph analysis, agent-based simulation, and custom software development.

Use Case Overview

The InnoRenew CoE's demonstrator "Noise Source Classification at the Edge" addresses a key urban challenge in the municipality of Koper, Slovenia—a coastal city of approximately 53,000 inhabitants. With a dual identity as both a residential hub and a tourist destination, Koper faces increasing pressure to manage environmental noise effectively. The influx of tourists, combined with local traffic and public events, contributes to rising noise levels that impact both the quality of life for residents and the overall urban soundscape. In response, the municipality is prioritizing IT-driven innovations to support smarter, data-informed city planning and governance.

A key area of interest for the city is the potential of solutions that enable real-time classification of environmental noise sources. Such a system would provide valuable insights to urban planners and decision-makers, helping them evaluate the impact of tourism, traffic, and public events on acoustic comfort. Traditional approaches rely on centralized architectures, where raw audio recordings are transmitted to the cloud for processing by machine learning models. While this setup enables advanced classification, it raises significant issues related to user privacy and system scalability.

To overcome these limitations, the demonstrator proposes an edge computing-based architecture driven by Swarmchestr^{ate}. By performing machine learning inference directly on the network of edge devices—close to where the data is generated—the solution ensures sensitive audio never leaves the local environment, thus preserving privacy. Moreover, it reduces the volume of transmitted data, enhancing scalability and energy efficiency. This approach aligns with the city's vision of adopting responsible and forward-looking

technologies that respect citizens' rights while delivering actionable insights for sustainable urban development.

Conceptual system design

Fig. 1. Conceptual system design

The system consists of a remote server and several edge devices, referred to as noise sensors. Each noise sensor includes a Raspberry Pi equipped with a noise meter for measuring sound pressure levels and an omnidirectional microphone for capturing audio. The device continuously monitors noise levels, and when a predefined threshold is exceeded, a 10 second audio segment recorded using the microphone is sent for classification. To optimize resource usage and manage thermal constraints, not all devices perform classification locally—audio may instead be forwarded to a nearby sensor currently handling classification. Task distribution and scaling across devices are managed by *Swarmchestrate*, which ensures efficient use of available resources. Classification results and noise level data are sent to a remote server, where they are stored in a time-series database and visualized through a monitoring dashboard.

Provide front-end, GUI screenshot (if applicable, available), as end users (or system operators) will see.

Fig. 2. Dashboard screenshot

Screenshot of the dashboard that end-users will interact with to view the collected data.

If there are different roles of persons using the system, list them what services they can use (e.g., system operator, system user).

The system users will access the dashboard where time-series data is displayed using a series of plots. The dashboard also allows the export of data at different levels of granularities for analysis.

Swarmchestrat Use Case

Swarmchestrat brings substantial benefits to the InnoRenew CoE's demonstrator, particularly in managing a network of edge devices operating under variable environmental conditions. Its decentralised orchestration framework allows the system to dynamically manage sound classification containers across edge devices based on real-time metrics such as CPU load and temperature.

This capability is especially valuable in our deployment scenario, where Raspberry Pi devices are exposed to different environmental conditions (e.g., direct sunlight), leading to varying thermal constraints. Swarmchestrat enables intelligent and adaptive load balancing by redirecting audio processing tasks to devices with available computational resources and lower operating temperatures. This not only helps maintain system performance and prevent thermal throttling but also increases the longevity and reliability of the devices.

Furthermore, Swarmchestrat facilitates a scalable and privacy-preserving architecture. Since the sound classification is performed at the edge, audio data never needs to be

transmitted to the cloud, addressing privacy concerns. At the same time, the decentralised orchestration ensures that the system remains responsive and efficient as the number of devices increases or usage patterns evolve.

What (process/development/deployment) needs to be changed to adapt to the Swarmchestrator implementation paradigm compared to traditional system design, development and operation?

Adopting Swarmchestrator involves several changes in how we design, develop, and operate our application compared to a traditional, centralized approach:

- **Containerized Microservices:** Core application components need to be containerized to allow Swarmchestrator to orchestrate them effectively.
- **Declarative Deployment Descriptors:** Instead of manual deployment, we need to provide formal descriptions of services (TOSCA), detailing scaling rules, hardware capabilities, service interconnections, etc.

This process ensures easy upgradability and adaptability of the system, supports seamless scaling, and simplifies testing and validation. In essence, Swarmchestrator provides a practical and effective approach that directly improves the deployment and operation of our edge-based application.

Users Description

The system involves several types of users, each contributing to the development, deployment, and usage of the application:

Developers

Developers are responsible for creating the container images and writing the application descriptors required for orchestration. They also develop and maintain the full-stack software infrastructure, including the visualization dashboard and the back-end system for data management. Additionally, they prepare software components that interface with the sensors on edge devices and ensure reliable data acquisition. Required competences include back-end and front-end development, containerization (e.g., Docker), orchestration concepts (Kubernetes, Swarmchestrator), experience with time-series databases (e.g., InfluxDB), and experience with IoT devices (e.g., Raspberry PI).

Operators

Operators are tasked with the physical setup, deployment, and maintenance of the sensors and edge devices. This includes configuring the devices, ensuring connectivity, and troubleshooting hardware in the field. They require practical knowledge on IoT systems, networking, and basic system administration.

End Users

End users interact with the system through the visualization dashboard. They can view

real-time and historical sensor data, monitor sound classification events, and export data for further analysis using external data tools. End users are typically domain experts or decision-makers and are not expected to have technical knowledge of the system's internal workings.

Business Model(s)

The development follows an open-source model, and the integration of Swarmchestrate does not alter the existing business model.

The business model is based on a contract that covers device preparation (sensors), installation, maintenance, and access to services such as data storage and the visualization dashboard. These services are typically provided under a **service** agreement for a defined period.

Use Case Requirements

Software Requirements

The use case relies entirely on open-source software, ensuring transparency, flexibility, and ease of integration. The following software components are used:

- **InfluxDB** – Time-series database used for storing sensor data and classification results. (*Open Source*)
- **ZeroTier** – Software-defined networking solution used to create a VPN among edge devices. (*Open Source*)
- **Grafana** – Visualization platform used for monitoring and exploring time-series data through dashboards. (*Open Source*)
- **Docker** – Containerization platform used to package and deploy application components on edge devices. (*Open Source*)
- **Linux** – Operating system running on the edge devices and server infrastructure. (*Open Source*)
- **OS Project Repository (InnoRenew CoE)** – Internal open-source codebase currently under development, containing modules for interfacing with sensors on the edge devices and other core functionalities specific to this use case.

System Requirements

Remote server for data storage and visualization:

- Linux based OS
- Hardware:
 - o 4 CPU cores

- o 16GB RAM
- o 200GB storage

Use-case specific devices:

- Raspberry PI 5 (docker enabled device)
- Sound pressure level sensor sensing range: 30dB – 120dB
- Omnidirectional microphone

Data Requirements

The system uses a self-hosted InfluxDB instance as a time-series database for storing sensor measurements and sound classification results. This solution is based on open-source software and deployed on a remote server managed by the InnoRenew team.

To ensure data availability and integrity, the system performs periodic database snapshots and supports offsite replication as part of the backup strategy.

Estimated Data Volume:

For a setup with 10 edge devices reporting sound pressure level (SPL) data once per second, the estimated data volume is approximately 4 MB per day. This volume does not include classification result data, which is significantly smaller in volume due to threshold-triggered event-based processing.

All data is stored on InnoRenew's infrastructure, maintained in accordance with standard data protection practices, and can be exported by end users for additional offline analysis.

External Services

No external services used.

Performance Requirements

To ensure a minimum quality of service (QoS) and stable operation of the system, the following performance criteria must be met:

Network Requirements

- **Minimum network bandwidth:** 5 MB/s
- **Network response time:** Ideally below **50 ms** for device-to-device communication over VPN to support real-time task redirection and coordination

Edge Device Requirements

- **CPU:** Minimum **quad-core processor clocked at 1.5 GHz**

- **RAM:** At least **4 GB**
These specifications are necessary to support real-time monitoring, local sound classification, and container-based orchestration while avoiding thermal throttling and resource contention.

These performance thresholds are required to maintain responsive operation of the system, timely processing of triggered audio events, and effective load balancing across the edge network.

Financial Requirements

N/A

Security Requirements

To ensure the safe operation of the system and protect sensitive data in transit, the following security measures are required:

- **Encrypted Communication:** All communication between edge devices must occur over a secure, encrypted channel. This is achieved through the use of a VPN established via ZeroTier, ensuring confidentiality and integrity of data exchanged across the network.
- **Access Control:** Only authorized devices and users should be able to access the network and system services. VPN membership is restricted and managed centrally to prevent unauthorized access.
- **System Hardening:** Edge devices and servers must be regularly updated and monitored to minimize exposure to known vulnerabilities.

These measures collectively ensure a secure and privacy-respecting edge computing environment suitable for urban sensing deployments.

Other Requirements

N/A

2.4.4 Demonstrator 4 requirements

UST

Company

Company Overview

UST is a multinational digital services company. Headquartered in the USA it has 35000 employees worldwide and operates in c.30 countries. The main EU hub is located in Spain

with c.1500 employees. There is also a large office in the UK. The company provides both closed projects and outsourcing for IT across the whole spectrum (hosting, integration, user interfaces, support, cybersecurity, IOT, blockchain and AI) for business in the financial, retail, manufacturing, insurance and telecom sectors.

Core Competencies & Expertise

In comparison with similar providers in the sector, one of UST's core competences is higher standards of customer service.

Clients (if applicable)

UST serves customers from all vertical sectors. In general clients tend to be very large organisations such as Santander Bank, Levi, Walmart and Sony.

Relevant Experience in Cloud & Edge Computing

Yes, UST is proficient at providing cloud solutions to its clients and using cloud services within internal and client projects.

Access to Cloud

UST is proficient at providing cloud solutions to its clients and using cloud services within internal and client projects.

UST is a high volume user of public cloud services, Azure, Google Cloud, IBMCloud and AWS.

Motivation for Participating in this Demonstration

UST is expecting to gain expertise in deploying edge devices in challenging environments as exemplified by the La Chanta site, and to extrapolate the learnings to other sites with similar complexity including both natural environments and industrial sites.

Type of Application

UST is building a Digital Twin of a natural system.

This Digital Twin is enriched with information extracted from several edge devices (IoT) that measure different environmental attributes such as those related to weather (humidity, temperature, wind direction and component...) and others more specific and relevant for environmental research, such as water characteristics from a wetland close by (ph. and electroconductivity).

The solution is presented using a map (browser webApp) that offers a graphical representation of the natural environment under observation. This map can represent all the devices that contribute with data about the space and allows the user to select and navigate through date intervals so that they can reinforce their research activity with accurate data about the system under study.

Use Case Overview

Use Case Motivation and Objectives

The use case builds a digital twin of a nature reserve. This is a site that was previously a working quarry and is now partially restored, and protected, allowing different flora and fauna to reclaim the space, such as nesting birds, amphibians and wild flowers.

The motivation is twofold. It will allow UST to develop skills and competences from overcoming challenges related to energy consumption and source, and data transmission limitations. These can be extrapolated for commercial exploitation in other scenarios. It will allow the nature reserve better insight into the variables that affect the system.

Use Case High-level Architecture

The solution has been designed sticking to very specific requirements established for the adequate restoration of the environment under study, hence usual technical elements that are generally considered a commodity (such as sustained electric current of sufficient broadband connectivity) are not regularly available at the site.

Considering these constraints, the architecture has been defined using devices with the smallest environmental footprint that could be used. Due to their broad adoption and openness, raspberry PI devices have been used to service the core of the infrastructure.

To ensure visibility and the capacity to offer to a broader audience a limited set of the capacities of the Digital Twin deployed at the space, a DR-like replica of these elements is deployed on a cloud-based service to replicate behaviour.

The diagram below offers a high-level overview of the infrastructure components that form part of the designed solution and how they are connected between them to deliver the overall service of the Digital Twin.

Fig. 1. Use case high-level architecture

Current Users

The system is designed for two different roles:

- **System Administrator:** Is the person responsible for updating configuration of the Digital Twin.
- **Operator:** This role can request, prepare and extract data sets of information of the system and have them presented on the UI.

Additionally, we can consider Digital Twin viewers – who receive information about the site from expert stakeholders aided by the digital twin. Includes school children, ecologists and other stakeholders.

Deployment Process

The solution is serviced using standard Open-Source solutions and elements that are already in the market, such as Kubernetes, ansible, helm... and is developed using common and extended languages such as Python and NodeJS (JavaScript).

For the code maintenance, UST has its own methodology and best practices that are applied along the overall lifecycle of the Digital Twin, using a combination of standard practices and artifacts (such as concurrent versioning systems, standard test execution plans and pipeline execution through automated tasks)

User Interface

For the Operator Role, which is the standard and more used role expected for the service, the system offers a UI that represents the Digital Twin Map, in which any of the available and connected IoT devices are presented for visualisation.

The system administrator, though, requires a more technical approach to interact, with specific changes in the configuration files that later must be populated to the running infrastructure. This mechanism generally requires the deletion or update of specific components and containers from the live service. This kind of task is delivered following any standard “pass to production” process as UST delivers for any technological customer.

Technologies, Platforms and Services Used

Raspberry Pis are the selected “edge device” to service the common infrastructure.

It relies on OpenSource technologies (K3S Rancher) to orchestrate the software running on the Raspberry Pis for the deployment and execution of the different components.

The solution is built using a Microservices approach that uses Docker Containers to run the different features, and uses a Synology NAS device to share, via NFS, a RAID replicated folder where all the data related to the digital twin is maintained.

NodeJS (JavaScript) and Python are the main languages selected for the development.

For data extracted from the IoT devices (due to their configuration and environment restrictions) we rely on several external services to gather data, such as EcoWitt, Fuelics and Hach’s.

Challenges or Limitations

- Due to the location and specific rehabilitation requirements, the solution does not have sustained Electric Power nor Internet Connectivity, and it must run as an isolated solution without relying on external (cloud) elements.
- To achieve this, the solution relies on the energy produced by several Solar Panels that is stored in batteries of the system.
- It has a schedule enabled Internet connection to avoid using it during work hours (8AM-5PM).
- When there’s no battery/enough solar light intensity, the Solution should run with the minimal components (reduced amount of Raspberry Pis).

Swarmchestrator Use Case

Expected Benefits of using Swarmchestrator

Swarmchestrator will allow us to deploy edge devices more efficiently. The devices will be able to operate over a longer period of time with less human intervention. They will allow a more powerful digital twin than would otherwise be possible considering the site limitations on bandwidth, energy and simultaneous uses of the site, concurrent users of the resources, unpredictability of the energy generation, etc.

Required Adaptation Efforts

Still under study, current detected items:

- Application description
- Infrastructure exposure to the internet
- Infrastructure DR design

Enumerate the list of “users” of the system, which may include developers and testers (who develop container images/application descriptors) of the application, operator (who deploys and monitors), end users (who use the application).

For each user, specify what they will do, and what competencies are needed (e.g. programming/orchestration concepts/Swarmchestrate system/Kubernetes, domain competence).

The system is designed for several different roles:

- System Administrator: Is the person responsible for updating configuration of the Digital Twin.
- Operator: This role can request, prepare and extract data sets of information of the system and have them presented on the UI.
- Developers: these were not mentioned in the previous question, they are responsible for the execution of the changes and fixes that appear during the software lifecycle. It is their responsibility, in agreement with the System Administrator, to ensure the automated and manual pipelines are invoked when appropriate.
- Digital Twin Viewers – do not require specific competences.

Business Model(s)

The development is a private, one-off development bespoke to the nature reserve. However, the concept can be replicated in other sites, extended into greater detail or extrapolated to scenarios with similar challenges.

We can generalise to a UST offering for digital twin modelling of complex locations. This would be a consulting, implementation and maintenance offering. It would be bespoke in each case but draw upon common components and architecture, with adaptations depending on purpose and site specifics (e.g. different sensors, different style of digital twin).

The Swarmchestrate solution could lower costs through permitting achieving the same level of detail with fewer sensors(less capex) and reducing the need for cabling (capex) or manual battery replacement (capex and opex). Furthermore it could allow viable digital twins to be developed for sites or use cases where today they are unfeasible, for example, due to difficulties in physically accessing sensors once they have been installed (e.g. to replace batteries) or where a very low energy footprint infrastructure is required.

The business model would be fee-based contracts.

Use Case Requirements

Software Requirements

OS: raspbian (Debian bookworm and bullseye)

Digital Twin: own development

System Requirements

Raspberry PI 5: (3 items) 16 GB RAM, 64GB SDCard

Raspberry PI 2B+: (5 items) 4GB RAM, 64GB SDCard

Synology NAS ds223: (1 item) 4Tb RAID1 capacity

Indicate preferred clouds (if used).

Solution is designed “cloud agnostic” but relies, at this moment of the design phase, on an Azure VM instance to service the DR replica of the solution components.

Enumerate use case-specific devices (e.g., edge devices, sensors, connectivity option).

EcoWitt WS68 as the weather array, accompanied by a WS6210 to work as Datalogger and core communication component for each weather station.

Fuelics Water Depth sensor for each wetland depth measurement.

Hach’s custom built suitcase for water characterisation measurement.

20 x 1Gb ethernet switch for components connectivity.

3G/4G connectivity for the IoT devices, as there are heavy restrictions on the extension of any radiofrequency based connectivity option, which already discards the deployment of any Wi-Fi based approach to connectivity.

Data Requirements

Still under design, most of the data used to maintain the Digital Twin will be sourced from JSON files that keep data in a per day/per device manner.

Estimate the amount of data produced/processed/exchanged (if applicable).

Data is of very small size, estimating less than 1Kb per device and day.

Describe briefly where/how these will be stored (maintained, replicated, backed up, ...).

Data is maintained on-site in a NAS device (Synology) from which it is made available using NFS file protocol.

Do you already have cloud storage in a public cloud provider e.g. AWS, Azure, ...?

This is not expected as part of the solution, which should be on-premises.

External Services

EcoWitt weather data service: Cloud based service that enables weather stations to upload their daily measurement. Data is retrieved from here using API methods at specific time intervals.

Fuelics Sensors Data Service: Cloud based service that enables Fuelics' sensors to upload their water depth measurements. Data is acquired from here by the solution using API methods.

Hach's Sensors data service: Cloud based service that enables Hach's devices to upload their measures to make them available. These can be acquired for the digital twin by an API communication with their site.

Performance Requirements

This cannot be answered at present – further work establishing the baseline is required before QoS goals can be defined.

Financial Requirements

Efficiency is important because frequent or extensive site access is neither financially viable nor compatible with the mission of the site.

Security Requirements

There is no public access to the site nor are the digital services available to the general public. The data in itself is not considered highly sensitive or particularly commercially confidential per se, nonetheless it is not for general consumption and specific parts of the data, such as those data used for as-yet unpublished scientific research must remain unpublished until the research itself is published.

QoS Requirements

There are no significant requirements, but there must not be major delays on data management. Furthermore:

- 7am-7pm running Digital Twin, for up to 50 concurrent users.
- No more than 2 days of data delay on retrieval, preferably UpToDate data.
- No more than one hour delay for processed data.
- No more than 24 hours delay on sync between Digital Twin instances (on Prem and D.R.).

Energy Consumption Requirements

Solar power is the unique source of energy.

Do you have energy consumption constraints for Cloud & Edge Resources (e.g. kWh/application or kWh/month)?

Not in a concrete manner, but the service is very dependent on solar energy and light availability. A solution has been designed to have a minimal electric footprint. Current consumption requirements are shown in the table below.

Tbl 1. Consumption of various devices

POWER SUPPLY COMPONENTS													
Device	battery?	capacity	Input Voltage	Input AC Frequency	Output Voltage	Output Current	Output Power(W)	Efficiency	Load Power Consumption (W)	No-Load Power Consumption	#devices	loadPowerCons (W)	zeroPowerCons (W)
rsppb2b	no		100-240V	50-60Hz	5.1V	3.0A	15	84%	12.6	0.05	5	63	0.25
rsppb5	no		100-240V	50-60Hz	5.1V	5.0A	25.5	85.50%	21.8025	0.1	3	65.4075	0.3
weather	yes	4800mAh	5-15V		5V	1A	0.85	85%	0.7225	0.06	1	0.7225	0.06
NAS			100-240V	50-60Hz			60W		17.343	4.08	1	35.143	17.28
NAS - drives			12V		12V	2A (max)	8-15W		8.9	6.6	2	17.8	13.2
NAS - case			100-240V	50-60Hz			60W		17.343	4.08	1	17.343	4.08
											Total	164.273	17.89

BATTERY BASED DEVICES (OUTDOORS)													
Device	battery?	capacity	Input Voltage	Input AC Frequency	Output Voltage	Output Current	Output Power(W)	Efficiency	Load Power Consumption (W)	No-Load Power Consumption	#devices	loadPowerCons (W)	zeroPowerCons (W)
weather	yes	4800mAh	5-15V		5V	1A	0.85	85%	0.7225	0.06	2	1.445	0.12
waterheight	yes		5-15V						0.5	0.05	2	1	0.1
watercharac	yes		5-15V		12V	1A					1	0	0
Solar Panel	yes	4800mAh	5-15V		12V	1A	7		0.05	0.05	2	0.1	0.1
											Total	2.545	0.32

Other Requirements

Solution is to be deployed on-premise, the DR replica will be made available only in the European Region, primarily in Spain.

2.5 Summary

This section presented the demonstrator applications, their main objectives, some technical details about the infrastructure, the types of sensors they use, and the high-level architecture. It also described the methodology used to assess and collect their requirements. We presented the questionnaire to assess the requirements of applications, which aimed to be as general as possible to cover potential later candidates as well. Finally, we added the actual questionnaires filled out by the individual demonstrators.

3. System Design

The Swarmchestrate project addresses key challenges in the orchestration of distributed, heterogeneous systems across the Cloud-to-Edge Continuum. At its core, it leverages **AI-driven orchestration** to enable seamless, simultaneous access to and intelligent use of resources from multiple providers. This ensures that application components are efficiently deployed and managed across diverse environments, optimising performance and adaptability.

Figure 5 Main challenges of the Swarmchestrate project

To support robust operation, **resilience** is built into the system's design, allowing it to dynamically respond to workload shifts, component failures, or network degradation. At the same time, **interoperability** is a guiding principle, where Swarmchestrate avoids vendor lock-in through standardised resource and application templates, facilitating smooth integration across platforms. Underpinning all orchestration decisions is **trust**, which ensures secure, reliable, and timely coordination across nodes, particularly crucial in decentralised and autonomous edge environments.

The purpose of this section is to introduce the system design of the Swarmchestrate Orchestration System. The system design detailed in this section will focus on the high-level integration of further consisting software systems, called subsystems.

Integration of several cooperating software subsystems requires the synchronization of their roles, functionalities, interfaces and operations. As a consequence, the purpose of this section is to detail how the subsystems are going to cooperate in order to realise the decentralised orchestration of cloud/edge resources and orchestration of microservice-based applications in the Swarmchestrate system.

Internal architecture and internal operation of the various subsystems building up the overall Swarmchestrate system is not part of this document. Internal details of the subsystems are described in other deliverables of the project.

High-level system design of the Swarmchestrate system has not been directly influenced by the demonstrators introduced in Section 2. The approach we followed during the project

started with an initial system design based on high-level goals. After the initial design has been created, we examined the demonstrators and introduced some fine-tuning of the Orchestration system handling the applications. The high-level design then was finalised and based on the low-level requirements of the demonstrators, the implementation of the different subsystems will be realised to provide compatibility with the requirements of the demonstrators.

3.1 Integrated Swarmchestrator System

Swarmchestrator Orchestration System will be a decentralised application-level orchestrator, based on the notion of self-organised interdependent Swarms. Resources are governed by agents where the requirements of submitted applications are fulfilled as a result of cooperation supported by intelligent matchmaking functionalities such as normal or private scoring.

Swarm is created when required resources are available and reserved. Newly created Swarms are then capable of dynamically self-organising themselves and are able to update their existing resource or application related configuration by applying intelligent (AI-driven) decision mechanisms. Decisions may include adding/removing (cloud/edge) resources or microservice instances of the application.

Monitoring of resources, microservices and other relevant details of the swarm will be realised in order to deliver appropriate information for the intelligent decision mechanism supporting matchmaking and reconfiguration.

Storing resource characteristics or information collected by the decentralised monitoring system will be realised by a decentralised knowledge base subsystem to support matchmaking and personalised reconfiguration decisions.

Transparency and trust among the stakeholders (e.g. resources, providers, etc.) in a Cloud-to-Edge continuum will be supported by a decentralised trust and identity system relying on blockchain technology.

In order to improve decision making, simulation will be applied running in parallel with the physical system, providing continuous feedback. This will be realised by a Digital Twin integrated into the overall system.

3.1.1 Subsystems

The following (sub)systems will be integrated in order to realise the Decentralised Swarmchestrator System:

Orchestration Subsystem: an application-level decentralised orchestration framework (incorporating compute, data and code), utilising Swarm-based distributed intelligence for highly dynamic and distributed Cloud-to-Edge computing infrastructures. Detailed description of this system can be found in Deliverable D2.1 “Decentralised Orchestrator Early Release”.

Scoring algorithm/subsystem: it is a component/system which evaluates the resources in relation to the requirements specified by the application and assigns ranking values. It has an important role in the resource selection process. It has two variants: private and non-private scoring, where the first one operates on encrypted data. Detailed description of the private scoring system can be found in Deliverable D3.1 “Definition of Trust and initial design of the trust and privacy management systems”, while D1.1 “Logical proximity and distributed matchmaking algorithms” introduces the non-private scoring algorithm.

AI subsystem: this subsystem is providing AI-driven intelligence used for matchmaking of resources and applications as well as for decision making in relation to reconfiguration of application components and resources. Detailed description of the private scoring system can be found in Deliverable D1.1 “Logical proximity and distributed matchmaking algorithms”.

Monitoring subsystem: distributed monitoring system responsible for collecting dynamic information about the application and resource entities and for generating alerts for preconfigured events happening. Detailed description of this system can be found in Deliverable D2.1 “Decentralised Orchestrator Early Release”.

Knowledge Base subsystem: a decentralised knowledge-preserving subsystem responsible for preserving and developing knowledge collected from the entire system to assist decisions related to applications and resources. Detailed description of this system can be found in Deliverable D3.1 “Definition of Trust and initial design of the trust and privacy management systems”.

Trust and Identity subsystem: a decentralised, block-chain based trust and identity management system responsible for evaluating resources in respect to their trustiness to support ranking and matchmaking with applications. Detailed description of this system can be found in Deliverable D3.1 “Definition of Trust and initial design of the trust and privacy management systems”.

Digital Twin: a simulation engine running in parallel with the real Swarmchestrator system focusing on discovering future trends and events to provide prediction for orchestration decisions. The simulation subsystem (that will form the basis of the Digital Twin) is described in Deliverable D4.2 “Design, development and evaluation of the Cloud-to-Edge simulator”.

The next section will give an overview on how the aforementioned Swarmchestrator components or subsystems are integrated.

3.1.2 High-level architecture, interfaces and integration

The architecture of the integrated, decentralised orchestration system can be seen in Figure 6. This section gives an overview of the overall operation focusing on the interfaces and interactions between the various components/subsystems. In Figure 6, the interactions between the different subsystems are enumerated in order to ease the understanding of the explanation for the interaction flow as described next.

The lifecycle of a Swarm starts with the submission of an application. The Orchestration subsystem receives the **Application Description (1)** from the Application Operator. The **Application Description (2)** is then preserved in the Knowledge Base. To deploy the Application, the Orchestration subsystem generates various, competitive resource offers based on the **Capacity Descriptions (2)** stored in the Knowledge Base. The last two steps are depicted as one interaction between the two subsystems.

The **Resource Offers (3)** are collected and forwarded to the Scoring subsystem which then performs the ranking representing the **Deployment Decision (4)** over the potential resources.

In the next phase, the Orchestration system interacts with both the cloud/edge resources to perform **Resource Management (5)** and the Kubernetes execution environment to realise **Application Management (6)**. During this deployment phase, resources are reserved and microservices are instantiated.

The actual setup of resources as well as the layout of the application belonging to the swarms are continuously rescued/stored into and retrieved from the Knowledge Base subsystem as **Capacity status information (7)** and **Swarm status information (8)**.

In order to collect dynamic information about the resources and swarms, the Monitoring system is instructed by registering the **Metric model (9)**. During the deployment of the application, the Application related metric exporters are also deployed, which during their execution feed the Monitoring system with **Metrics (10)**. When the metric values are collected and specific events occur, the Monitoring system forwards the **Metrics & SLO violations (11)** related to both application and resources to the Orchestration subsystem for further consideration.

During the lifetime of the Swarm, **Metrics & events (12)** relevant for reconfiguration are continuously forwarded by the Orchestration system upon requesting **Reconfiguration decision (13)** from the AI-driven intelligent subsystem. **Composite Metrics & SLO violations (14)** information - which is a subset of Metrics & events used by the AI-driven intelligent subsystem - is also persisted by the Knowledge Base system for future processing.

In parallel to these activities, the Trust management system collects information such as **Capacity Description (15)** and **Composite metrics & SLO violations (16)** to evaluate the resources and to generate associated **Trust value (17)(18)** for the Orchestration system through the Knowledge Base for consideration when resources are selected.

Digital Twin is continuously executing in the background parallel to the previously mentioned subsystems. It collects **Capacity status (19)**, **Swarm status (20)**, **Application and Capacity Description (21)** from the Knowledge Base as well as the dynamic **Metrics & SLO violations (22)** from the Monitoring system. As a result, Digital Twin with a simulation performed inside is able to generate **Application and Resource Management recommendations (23)** to the Orchestration System for consideration.

Figure 6 High-level interface design of the Orchestration Subsystem

The description above summarised the interactions to demonstrate the integration of the aforementioned subsystems forming the overall Swarmchestrator system. The overall interactions and operation designed and introduced may change during the next phase of the project as integration takes place. The next subsections will give a short summary of the individual subsystems focusing on their interfaces, interactions, internal components and deployment. Please, note that detailed internal operation of the subsystems are detailed in other deliverables of this project.

3.2 Decentralised Orchestration

The Decentralised Orchestration subsystem is responsible for governing and managing resources, for deployment of new swarms to run applications consuming the resources and for providing an environment to support self-management of swarms including self-reconfiguration towards their QoS requirements.

Resources are considered to be cloud resources (e.g. virtual machines) and edge devices (e.g. physical devices). The utilisation of these resources are coordinated by the

Orchestration System. Resources are assigned to swarms at deployment time as well as in case of reconfiguration during their lifetime.

Swarms are self-managing entities deployed by the Decentralised Orchestration System. After deployment, the Decentralised Orchestration System supports swarms with resource-related, reconfiguration-related and qos-related reconfigurations through the management of an environment consisting of functionalities such as monitoring, decision-making, resource-selection and knowledge-management.

The environment responsible for providing the aforementioned groups of functionalities is built by several subsystems with which the Decentralised Orchestration System is realising intensive cooperation. High-level interface design of the Decentralised Orchestration detailing the nature of the links is introduced next.

3.2.1 High-level interface

This section summarises the high-level interface of the Orchestration Subsystem to the other subsystems in the Swarmchestrator system. The Orchestration Subsystem is represented as one box with all its inputs on the left side and with all its outputs on the right side.

The following **inputs** (see left side of Figure 7) are designed as part of the Orchestration subsystem:

- 1) **Application Description**: a detailed description of the application to be submitted to be orchestrated. Description consists of resource specification, list of microservices with their detailed definition and QoS related requirements. Application Descriptor is submitted to the Orchestration Subsystem by a so-called Application Operator.
- 2) **Resource Management (Query)**: represents all information collected from the underlying swarm owned resources such as cloud and edge resources through the Cloud API and Edge interface. These may include for example the status of the virtual machines and internal attributes edge device where no monitoring system is utilised.
- 3) **Application Management (Query)**: represents all information collected from the underlying kubernetes cluster hosting the swarm and its application through the kubernetes API. These may include the status of the application containers and their placement inside the kubernetes cluster where no monitoring system is utilised.
- 4) **Metrics & events**: during the lifetime of the overall Swarmchestrator system various metrics related to applications/swarms and resources are measured by the Monitoring subsystem and made available as events for the Orchestration subsystem. These metrics are necessary inputs for scheduling, orchestration and resource management.
- 5) **Deployment decision**: covers the selection of the resources associated with the swarm hosting the newly submitted application. The calculation of the deployment decision is taken as input originating from the Scoring subsystem. The input covers a list of ranked potential resources offered to host the target swarm.

6) **Reconfiguration decision:** covers the manipulation of the resources associated to the swarm and/or the update/reconfiguration of any metrics related to the application. The calculation of the reconfiguration decision is taken as input originating from the AI subsystem. The input may cover various decisions e.g. up or downscaling of resources or application components such as microservices.

7) **Capacity Description:** a detailed description of a set of resources that will be used for hosting the applications to be executed within swarms. Description of the Capacities are stored in the Knowledge Management subsystem that provides access for the Orchestration Subsystem when necessary.

Figure 7 High-level interface design of the Orchestration Subsystem

8) **Capacity status information:** the actual status of resources in terms of allocation. The Orchestration subsystem requires this information as input to discover the available

(unused) resources that can be offered for the swarm that will host the newly submitted application. This information is designed to be stored by the Knowledge Management subsystem.

9) **Swarm status information:** the actual status of the swarm in terms of its components and associated resources. The Orchestration system will manage multiple swarms for which status information must be persisted. The input side represents the capability to get the status information persisted previously. This functionality is provided by the Knowledge Management subsystem.

10) **Trust value:** Trust value associated with cloud and edge resources is considered by the Orchestration System during the selection of the resources for the swarms.

11) **Application and Resource Management Recommendations:** recommendations related to application or resource management may arrive from the Digital Twin during the lifetime of the swarm, recommendations are considered by the Orchestration System.

The following **outputs** (see right side of Figure 7) are designed as part of the Orchestration subsystem:

1) **Resource management:** The Orchestration subsystem is responsible for preparing, instantiating Cloud or Edge resources that will host a kubernetes cluster to execute Application components. As a consequence the Orchestration subsystem must interface with Cloud APIs Cloud or Edge endpoints to Create, Update or Delete the instantiated resource entities.

2) **Application management:** The Orchestration subsystem is responsible for the deployment of a Kubernetes cluster to execute Application components. Furthermore, the Orchestration subsystem must also interface with the Kubernetes cluster to Create, Update or Delete microservices to realise Swarm and its Application.

3) **Metric Model:** The Monitoring system is going to deliver the values of metrics required for performing reconfiguration related decisions. In order to monitor the required metrics the Orchestration system is going to notify the Monitoring subsystem about the list of metrics represented by a so-called Metric Model.

4) **Resource Offers:** for the submitted applications new resource/capacity offers are generated by the Resource Agents. These offers must be evaluated i.e. scored according to the various attributes of the offered resources. This output interface covers the request sent towards the Scoring subsystem to perform scoring functionality for a new set of resources.

5) **Application Description:** in order to persist this information, the submitted application description is stored in the Knowledge Management subsystem.

6) **Metrics & events for reconfiguration:** this interface covers the information flow from the Decentralised Orchestration to the AI subsystem in order to let the AI perform decisions in relation to Swarms to realise self-organisation and management. The input for the AI must cover all related metrics and events that may influence the behaviour of the Swarm.

7) **Capacity status information:** the actual status of resources in terms of allocation which helps discover the available (unused) resources that can be offered for Swarms. The Orchestration subsystem persists this information as output towards the Knowledge Management subsystem.

8) **Swarm status information:** the actual status of the swarm in terms of its components and associated resources. The Orchestration system will manage multiple swarms for which status information must be persisted by the Knowledge Management subsystem.

The aforementioned high-level interfaces are currently specified for the Decentralised Orchestration subsystem. Low-level details of the interfaces are not part of this document, it is an ongoing work.

3.2.2 Internal components

Decentralised Orchestration subsystem consists of two important components, such as Resource Agent and Swarm Agent.

Resource Agent (RA) is designed to be the representative for Capacities describing a set of Cloud or Edge resources. The Resource Agent is responsible to manage the capacity registered for it, i.e. it allocates or releases resources of the capacity to different Swarms based on incoming requests. Resource management is realised by cooperating with other Resource Agents to discover available and matching resources for new swarms. Resource Agents are also responsible to provide an endpoint for Swarm handling, i.e. to implement functionalities such as submission, management, query or removal of Swarms. Finally, the Resource Agent is initiating the birth of the Swarms by preparing resources and launching Swarm Agents as part of the deployment process.

Swarm Agent (SA) is a core component of the Decentralised Orchestration subsystem and is responsible for managing a Swarm's lifecycle and behaviour as being part of it. Multiple Swarm Agents may exist and operate within a Swarm, collectively ensuring its resilience and autonomy by handling tasks such as monitoring, self-organisation, and dynamic reconfiguration.

A third component of the Decentralised Orchestration system is a **Client** component that provides an interface for humans to interact with the network of Resource Agents to submit, update, query or remove Swarms. Primarily this component serves as a convenient way of interacting with the Swarmchestrator system for the Application Operator, it can be either command-line, graphical user interface or both.

3.2.3 Deployment of components

In this section, the deployment of the components belonging to the Orchestration Subsystem is summarised.

Resource Agent is a (micro)service that is intended to join the network of Resource Agents and is responsible to represent the capacity registered for it. As a consequence, a Resource Agent is a continuously running service that must be deployed by the operator, preferably close to the capacity the RA will handle.

Swarm Agent is a microservice running inside the kubernetes cluster of the Swarm and is deployed at the time of birth of the Swarm automatically by the Resource Agent. Swarm Agent is running during the lifetime of the Swarm and may replicate itself in certain situations.

The **Client** component is a command-line tool (optionally with graphical user interface) that can be deployed and executed at a location from where it is able to access one of the Resource Agents interconnected. The client can be launched by individuals to be used personally.

3.3 Scoring subsystem

In the deployment phase each Resource Agent (RA) may offer its resources to the lead RA requesting on behalf of an application. In scenarios with multiple RAs offering a variety of resources, the scoring algorithm determines the resources that will actually be allocated for the application. For that purpose the attributes of the resources offered are compared with the requirements of the application. For each requirement a score may be determined. Aggregation of such scores leads to a final score for a resource or set of resources.

The alternative private scoring algorithm enables resource selection without exposing sensitive attributes. Instead of processing raw resource descriptions, the scoring is performed on encrypted data using verifiable functional encryption. This ensures that even the lead RA cannot access the actual attribute values while still computing accurate scores. The algorithm outputs a final score for each resource offer similar to the non-private scoring algorithm.

3.3.1 High-level interface

Figure 8 High-level interface design of the Scoring Subsystem

The RAs belong to the orchestration subsystem and they utilise both the private and non-private scoring algorithm variants with the information they need about the requirements of the application as well as the available resources. The result is returned to the RAs as well, which means that the scoring subsystem has interfaces only with the orchestration subsystem.

3.3.2 Internal components

Both scoring algorithms are implemented as single code libraries and as such fully integrated within the orchestration subsystem. Both private and non-private scoring provide the same interface, making them interchangeable and allowing seamless substitution depending on the privacy requirements of the deployment context.

3.3.3 Deployment of components

The scoring algorithms are deployed as part of the Resource Agent that will utilise the scoring functionalities.

3.4 AI-driven Intelligence

The resources selected in the deployment process are chosen using the application's requirements including its QoS specifications. While the application is running the execution environment could violate the specified QoS goals due to several reasons, e.g. overload of resources or network congestion. The AI subsystem uses monitoring data and the information about QoS goals to build models of the different application components. Those are used to carry out short-term predictions on how the QoS metrics will change.

If a violation is detected or predicted, the subsystem will propose adjustments to the application's configuration in order to establish a state where the application's QoS goals are met again.

3.4.1 High-level interface

Figure 9 High-level interface design of the AI Subsystem

The AI subsystem runs as code library inside or as a small service next to swarm agents (SAs) from the orchestration subsystem. It receives all relevant information about monitored application and node metrics from the SA. Proposed configuration changes will then be delivered to the SA in return as well.

3.4.2 Deployment of components

The AI subsystem runs inside or next to every SA and is set up at the same time. However, weaker systems, especially edge devices, that do not possess the computational capabilities to handle the AI subsystems' tasks are excluded. Their data will instead be processed on the closest system with an SA that is capable enough.

3.5 Monitoring System

The Event Monitoring System (EMS) being developed for the project, is responsible for monitoring the applications running through Swarmchestrator's technology and informing the orchestration module about violation occurrences based on thresholds set by the application owners. These SLO violations trigger application topology reconfigurations.

3.5.1 High-level interface

During deployment time, the monitoring system will receive as input the Metric Model in TOSCA [5] from the Orchestrator as part of the TOSCA description of the application from which it will be extracted in order to get the necessary monitoring information. During

runtime, the monitoring system will be getting two kinds of metrics as explained in detail in deliverable D2.1 , the infrastructure level metrics and the application level metrics. The first ones are going to be monitored directly from EMS agents using Netdata [6] and the second ones are going to be collected through metrics exporters developed by the application owners (or in our case from the demonstrators).After metrics processing has been completed , metrics and potential SLO violations are published through pub/sub channels called topics. In these topics the Orchestrator will be able to subscribe in order to receive them and use them or forward them to the AI components of the swarm. The Knowledge Base will also use the same technology to persist the composite metrics and the SLO violations needed in its modules.

Figure 10 High-level interface design of the Monitoring Subsystem

Finally, the Digital Twin will be able to subscribe to receive composite metrics and SLO violations in order to have an up-to-date representation of the system. The high-level diagram of the integration of the monitoring system is depicted in Figure 10.

3.5.2 Internal components

The Event Monitoring System consists of two kinds of components. The Event Processing Manager (EPM) and the Event Processing Agents (EPA). The Event Processing Manager is the controller of the Monitoring System for each application and it is unique per swarm. It is responsible for giving the necessary instructions to the monitoring agents for formulating the Event Processing Network to observe the quality of the deployed application as well as the monitoring specifications of each component of the application. It is also responsible for the final processing of the metrics' data received from the EPAs, propagating the composite metrics to the respective topics and generating SLO violations events in SLO related topics to alert the Orchestrator. EPAs are responsible for collecting the monitoring data from the microservices and for hosting infrastructure for each application component running on the swarm. They can apply the necessary complex event processing on the metrics collected and forward them to the EPM .

3.5.3 Deployment of components

The first component needed to be deployed is the Event Processing Manager (EPM), before any of the EPAs. The deployment of the EPM will take place by the Orchestrator, during the formation of the Swarm . When a user sends its application's monitoring requirements, the

EPM will translate and analyse the metric model to give event processing network formation directions on each EPA spawned by the Orchestrator. EPAs will be deployed by the orchestrator and will be present in each resource to be monitored (or nearby in cases of limited resource capacity).

3.6 Knowledge Management

The Knowledge Management (*hereinafter KM*) system within the Swarmchestrate system, acts as a decentralized intelligence layer contributing to enabling context-aware orchestration decisions. A key component to this system is the **Decentralized Knowledge Base (KB)**, which stores, updates, and distributes detailed descriptions of available resource metrics, application descriptions and capacity descriptions. It ensures that the orchestration system has timely access to relevant data when deciding optimal placements or performing dynamic reconfiguration. The decentralized KB leverages a number of **Knowledge Base Agents** (*hereinafter KB agents*) supporting fault-tolerant and federated orchestration logic by enabling each agent to function autonomously while contributing to a broader, synchronized system.

The **aim of the Decentralized KB** is to provide necessary extracted metadata and enable contextual matchmaking between application descriptors and available capacity, allowing the Knowledge Management system to serve as a trusted authority for provisioning, scheduling, and operational steering of applications. To that end, **key functionalities incorporate** the management of *dynamic metadata, validating information timeline, and efficient handling of decentralized queries without introducing a centralized bottleneck*. This is established through a mesh network of decentralized agents that interact and operate in a dual state. Each agent is equipped with persistent data stores comprising both mutable and immutable layers. Mutable stores are leveraged for updates and local state management, while the immutable stores preserve historical records and critical metadata.

The agents follow a twofold data interaction model. They prioritize the local first data access while ensuring global data consistency. This enables coherent and up-to-date views of the resource landscape, irrespective of the origin or location of data across the Swarmchestrate system. As a result, the KB component becomes instrumental in managing and maintaining the balance between local autonomy and global coherence, facilitating swarm-based orchestration information.

3.6.1 High-level interface

The KB component exposes multiple interfaces designed for modularity, extensibility, and necessary access either for the integration between KB agents but also with external systems like the Orchestration system, Trust Management system, Digital Twin, EMS and Capacity providers. The KB component offers different interaction paradigms, as follows:

- **Synchronous Request/Response** (*e.g., HTTP/REST*)
- **Asynchronous Publish/Subscribe** (*e.g., ipfs pub/sub*)
- **Peer-to-peer** (*e.g., libp2p*)

Table 1 describes the interactions, as depicted in Figure 11, in relation to the associated components or systems.

Table 1 Interactions between KM and other subsystems

System / Role	Datastore	Integration Scenario	Operation Type	Purpose
Orchestrator Subsystem	App Descriptions (ADT)	Submission	Persist (Insert)	Stores new application descriptors into KB
Orchestrator Subsystem	App Descriptions (ADT)	Matchmaking	Query (Retrieve)	Retrieves application descriptions for resource matching
Orchestrator Subsystem	New Deployment OpenTofu	Upload	Persist (Insert)	Stores uploaded validated templates
Orchestrator Subsystem	New Deployment OpenTofu	Validation	Query (Retrieve)	Retrieves stored templates for reuse/validation
Orchestrator Subsystem	Deployment Plans	Plan Generation	Persist (Insert)	Stores generated deployment plans
Orchestrator Subsystem	Deployment Plans	Plan Execution	Query (Retrieve)	Retrieves feasible deployment plans
Orchestrator Subsystem	Capacity Status	Resource Allocation	Persist (Insert)	Stores current resource allocation
Orchestrator Subsystem	Capacity Status	Pre-deployment Check	Query (Retrieve)	Retrieves available resources
Orchestrator Subsystem	Swarm Status	Swarm Deployment	Persist (Insert)	Stores swarm deployment state
Orchestrator Subsystem	Swarm Status	Monitoring	Query (Retrieve)	Retrieves current swarm deployment information
Capacity Provider	Capacity Descriptions	Resource Registration	Persist (Insert)	Stores new resource descriptions directly into KB for orchestration visibility
EMS	Composite Events /	Telemetry Streaming	Persist (Insert)	Inserts historical telemetry and SLO violation data

	Violation History			
Trust Management Subsystem	Capacity Descriptions	Trust Evaluation	Query (Retrieve)	Fetches capacity metadata for trust computation
Trust Management Subsystem	Composite Metrics & SLO Violations	Trust Calculation	Query (Retrieve)	Reads telemetry history for trust scoring
Trust Management Subsystem	Trust Scores	Trust Update	Persist (Insert)	Persists calculated trust scores back into KB
Digital Twin	Application & Capacity Descriptions	Simulation Init	Query (Retrieve)	Fetches full system state for simulations
Digital Twin	Capacity Status	Simulation Runtime	Query (Retrieve)	Reads live capacity allocation for scenario evaluation
Digital Twin	Swarm Status	Simulation Runtime	Query (Retrieve)	Retrieves swarm deployments for simulation accuracy

Each integration paradigm supports a respective interface exposed under a clear **input** (*request or command, reflected above as insert to persist data or query to request data*) and **output** (*response or event according to the input request*) supporting schema-defined payloads. However, it is deemed necessary to raise the nature of the KB acting as a responder rather than an initiator compared to the rest of Swarmchestrator, systems and components. The core interface considers a standardized Request/Response API (*i.e. HTTP*), allowing the rest of system components to retrieve, insert, or update resource knowledge. These interactions are mediated through an internal mechanism supporting semantic queries (*i.e. schema agnostic, context aware etc.*) that may range from simple attribute filters to composite, multi-metric evaluations.

The API supports fine-grained query definitions, enabling orchestrators to filter resources based on TOSCA based description and/or JSON related key value pairs that have been persisted after an interaction. A typical invocation considers parameters, *i.e.* resource class, operating threshold, required features, deployment region *etc.*, while the response considers invocation result that incorporates matching data entries and result of the context payload.

With regards to access of information amongst the KB agents, Role-based access control is enforced at the interface KB level, ensuring that only authorized agents can push updates, initiate sync events, or access certain knowledge layers. Integration with the authentication

layer of Swarmchestrator guarantees trust and auditability. The KB component is also designed with schema flexibility in mind, supporting JSON-based but also SQL-based payloads that accommodate respective data models under prescribed Data Stores for persisting data.

Figure 11 High-level interface design of the Knowledge Management Subsystem

3.6.2 Deployment of components

Assuming that t_0 is the starting instantiation point of the **orchestration environment**, the **Knowledge Base (KB)** is provisioned accordingly (*at least three KB agents³*) at the point where the system requires **semantic resource awareness, metadata-driven matchmaking, and decentralized state sharing** to support orchestration decisions. Thus, the KB is provisioned during the **bootstrap phase of Swarmchestrator** under a TOSCA based template, immediately after the initial discovery and registration of **Resource Agents (RA)** and prior to any application deployment or workload scheduling. The KB Agents are deployed as **standalone pods** or **sidecar containers** within a Kubernetes (*K3s*) clustered environment. The Coordinator Agent typically resides in *K3s* cluster nodes with higher availability and capacity, such as orchestrator-bound pods, or gateway agents in an edge cluster, whereas the Follower Agents due to the principle of merely supporting the **local-first intelligence**, can

³ According to principles followed in similar approaches of Raft, Paxos considering the $n = 2f + 1$ formula to tolerate **1 node failure**, considering **2 out of 3 nodes (majority)** to continue making progress -achieving quorum

be per swarm (*application related swarm, i.e. K3s application cluster*) under the Swarmchestrate topology.

A single **Coordinator Agent (KBc)** is instantiated per **Swarmchestrate Universe**, which encompasses all participating K3s clusters and orchestration components. This KBc acts as the semantic reasoning core and responds to northbound systems such as the orchestrator, AI planner, and EMS systems. To enable decentralized knowledge access at least **two Follower Agents (KBf)** are required. These KBf instances are deployed per **Swarm**, with each Swarm representing a K3s application cluster.

Table 2 Knowledge Base Agent deployment details

KB Agent Type	Recommended Count	Deployment Scope
Coordinator Agent (KBc)	1 per Swarmchestrate Universe/system	Deployed in a highly available K3s node (orchestrator pod or edge gateway)
Follower Agent (KBf)	≥ 1 per Swarm (i.e., per K3s application cluster)	Deployed as a sidecar or standalone pod in the Swarm
Sync Peer KB Agents	Optional, ≥ 1 for multi-agent setups, across different Swarms or within a large swarm	Need to synchronize knowledge across those agents to maintain consistency or improve query reach

3.7 Trust and Identity management

The trust management system in Swarmchestrate acts as a backbone for trustworthy interactions across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum within the Swarmchestrate universes. Anchored in a formal trust model, it blends self-sovereign identity (SSI) with decentralised identifiers (DIDs) to provide privacy-preserving, role-based credentials for the core entities (i.e. resource providers, resource capacities). New participants receive a DID and verifiable credentials at onboarding, without relying on a central identity provider; every subsequent interaction is authenticated, authorised, and a reputation score derived from immutable, on-chain evidence of past behaviour, policy compliance, and service-level performance.

3.7.1 High-level interface

The diagram below (Figure 12) is a high level representation of the Trust Management System. The system is composed of three tightly-coupled subcomponents. The Metric Aggregator pulls knowledge such as: capacity description, composite metrics (e.g. reputation, computing and network metrics) and events stored in the Knowledge Base. The Trust Calculator fuses these inputs with verifiable credentials and identities (DIDs) that reside on the blockchain, calculating the trust using a deterministic or stochastic algorithm. Finally, the Trust Certifier encapsulates each score in a verifiable credential, signs it and anchors its hash on the blockchain, creating an immutable certificate that anyone can later verify its integrity.

Inputs therefore arrive from two directions: capacity descriptions from Knowledge Management, and blockchain-resident data holding both historical reputation and identities for resource capacities and their providers. Outputs flow in the opposite direction: the freshly calculated trust value feeds the AI orchestration logic, the same value is written back into the Knowledge Base for analytics and planning, and the signed trust certificate is published to the blockchain so every stakeholder can cryptographically validate the score's provenance.

Figure 12 High-level interface design of the Trust and Identity Management System

All specifications covering the formal definition of trust, the exact calculation methodology, and an in-depth description of each component of the Trust Management System will be provided in deliverable D3.1.

3.7.2 Internal components

The Trust Management System is envisioned as a set of microservices with exposed API endpoints for communication with external components. Its internal components are the Trust Metric Aggregator, the Trust Calculator and the Trust Certifier. These components are explained in greater details in D3.1.

3.7.3 Deployment of components

The aforementioned elements are envisioned as Docker-based services, making the trust management reusable, scalable and easily integratable in the platform.

3.8 Digital Twin

In Swarmchestrat, a simulation solution, namely DISSECT-CF-Fog (for further information, see D4.2), is extended towards modelling the Cloud-to-Edge Continuum and it is used for providing the first testbed for evaluating and fine-tuning the proposed orchestration algorithms. Starting in M19, this simulation environment will be further extended to create a digital twin of the orchestration solution.

A DT creates virtualised models of physical systems and processes, supporting virtual prototyping, testing decisions in diverse scenarios, and incorporating both real-time and historical data. It runs in parallel with the physical system, providing continuous feedback [7]. Although simulation is a component of a DT, not all simulations qualify as digital twins, as they are distinct technologies. Utilising a DT involves four stages [8]:

- Representation: Focusing on data collection and the behavior of the physical system
- Replication: Duplicating the physical system in a virtual environment

- Reality: Using the DT to investigate scenarios and apply insights to the physical system
- Relational: The DT integrates decision-making technologies like AI and ML to enable bi-directional data exchange between the physical and digital systems

Currently, the design of Swarmchestrator's digital twin is in its early stage. Nevertheless, in this document, we outline our initial findings and next steps for its development.

The DT might be applied during both the deployment and runtime phases. At deployment time, when a new application is submitted, the DT could evaluate alternative deployment configurations by simulating their expected behavior and comparing them based on predicted performance and efficiency. During runtime, the DT could help evaluate the ongoing effectiveness of active deployments and explore operational decisions such as scaling, migration, or service adaptation in response to dynamic changes in the system.

The DT could support both proactive and reactive decision-making modes. In a proactive role, it would continuously analyse the system state and suggest actions to the orchestration subsystem. For instance, recommending the migration of a service to prevent potential overload. In contrast, it may also work reactively, where the orchestrator triggers it to simulate and assess the consequences of a planned operation, such as scaling an application component.

Finally, the DT may operate at different levels. It could focus on individual swarms, tracking the state and performance of a specific application and supporting localized management decisions. On a broader level, it might consider the global state of the entire Swarmchestrator environment, enabling system-wide analysis and optimizations.

3.8.1 High-level interface

The DT in Swarmchestrator is a component that collects data from various external subsystems, including metrics and event information from the Monitoring subsystem, as well as capacity and swarm status details, and the application description from the Knowledge Base subsystem. Based on these inputs, the DT maintains an up-to-date virtual representation of the physical system and gives recommendations to the Orchestration subsystem.

Figure 13 High-level interface design of the Digital Twin Subsystem

3.8.2 Internal components

The digital twin is envisioned as a Spring Boot service that provides the necessary API endpoints for communication with external components. Its internal components include the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator [9], and optionally, the scoring subsystem presented in Section 3.3, as well as the AI-driven intelligence described in Section 3.4.

3.8.3 Deployment of components

The aforementioned elements are packaged as a Docker-based service, making the digital twin reusable and scalable as needed. This enables the deployment of multiple instances to simulate various possible behaviors or scenarios of the system.

4. Demonstrator Specifications

In Section 2, the requirements of the demonstrators have been presented, which only estimated the implementation and integration efforts, at a high level (enumerating expected costs and benefits). That section presented only a conceptual system design (with the aim of understanding application goals, context and assessing whether the requirements can be met) but without showing how the various modules of the demonstrator will actually connect to the different Swarmchestrate core components.

This section proceeds further to present a more detailed specification, system design for the demonstrators, now considering integration aspects with Swarmchestrate technologies and toolsets. The results introduced in this section had been achieved by the demonstrators, but went through an evolution and were refined iteratively during the series of weekly telcos, where Swarmchestrate developers also assisted in improving the system design in order to be compliant with Swarmchestrate concepts and design principles. Several topic-specific telcos were organised to address specific integration details and answer implementation questions, with different working groups (Monitoring, Orchestration, AI teams).

This section presents the latest technical system design of each demonstrator, which includes all the microservices (now in a containerised form) the application decomposed to, their interactions, data flows, connections to external services and external databases, as well as particular connections to Swarmchestrate core components (orchestrator, monitoring system, etc.).

It is followed by enumerating the identified so-called “metrics” or events for which the Swarmchestrate system is expected to react in order to maintain the required system-level objectives (SLOs). These metrics need to be monitored continuously by the Swarmchestrate monitoring system, periodically checking potential violations, exceeding certain thresholds. Some of the metrics are provided by the Swarmchestrate system (more specifically, by the monitoring system) out-of-the-box, such as resource consumptions (e.g., CPU, memory usage), some needed customisation effort by the demonstrators to implement custom metric-exporters to raise “exotic” events (such as the current sunshine intensity, battery levels, number of active users, amount of data to be persisted in cloud) explicitly to the monitoring system .

In the last subsections, we report on the status of the initial implementation efforts.

4.1 Demonstrator 1 specification

This section presents the system design of the first demonstrator, followed by enumerating the list of identified metrics (that play an important role in scaling the application to maintain SLOs). Finally, a short status report on the prototype implementation closes this subsection.

4.1.1 Demonstrators System Design

The main components of the conceptual system design shown in Figure 14 are as follows (from left to right):

1. **IoT devices** The Fuelics devices that are deployed in the manholes
2. **IoT gateway** The software gateway that acts as the entry point for the bi-directional communication between the devices and the Fuelics IoT platform.
3. **Fuelics IoT platform containers** There are two groups of containers
 - 3.1 The purple coloured ones are the containers that provide the functionality of the IoT platform.
 - 3.2 The green/yellow/red ones are the containers that control the device reconfiguration. These are the containers that are actively managed by the Swarmchestrate orchestrator in order to adapt the devices' configuration to the expected weather conditions
4. **Monitoring subsystem** The Swarmchestrate service that will convert the application level metrics to Service Level Agreements (SLOs) which will in turn trigger the application reconfiguration
5. **Weather forecasting service** The external service that provides the forecast for the expected rainfall. The data from this service are converted to an application
6. **Cloud Database/Messaging** The cloud based database/monitoring service used by the Fuelics platform level metric by the Fuelics platform which is published to the monitoring service

Figure 14 System design of the Wastewater Manhole Management in Athens Metropolitan Sewage Network demonstrator

4.1.2 Metrics for Monitoring and Scaling

Table 3 enumerates the metric(s) used by this demonstrator application.

Table 3 Demonstrator 1 metrics

Metric name	Description	Influence on scaling/application	Unit
Maximum expected rainfall forecast for the next two days	The forecasted rainfall in a region for the next day. Multiple weather forecasting services may be queried to cover different regions.	Depending on the forecast, spawn reconfiguration containers for the predefined profiles based on expected rainfall mm (e.g. [0,10],[10,50][50,oo) -> Low, Medium, High rainfall configuration)	mm

4.1.3 Early prototyping

A summary of the results in early prototyping phase is as follows:

1. The deployment of 175 IoT devices in manholes is completed.
2. A first prototype of the service that will retrieve the external weather data forecast is available.
3. The implementation of the services that will perform the reconfiguration of the devices based on profiles for the forecasted rainfall is in progress.

In regards to the deployment of the IoT devices, the installation started on June 1st and is progressing at a rate of 10 to 20 devices per day. The completion of the installation is expected by the end of June. Some indicative pictures from the areas in front of Olympiacos FC Stadium and Microlimano in Akti Koumoundourou next to the Sailing Club are listed below.

Figure 15 IoT device installation at Olympiacos FC Stadium and Microlimano

4.2 Demonstrator 2 specification

This section presents the system design of the second demonstrator, followed by enumerating the list of identified metrics. Finally, a short status report on the prototype implementation closes this subsection.

4.2.1 Demonstrators System Design

The main components of the conceptual system design shown in Figure 16 are as follows (from left to right):

1. **IoT devices** The Fuelics parking space monitoring devices that are deployed.
2. **IoT gateway** The software gateway that acts as the entry point for the bi-directional communication between the devices and the Fuelics IoT platform.
3. **Fuelics IoT platform** containers There are two groups of containers
 - 3.1 The purple coloured ones are the containers that provide the functionality of the IoT platform.
 - 3.2 The green/blue ones are the containers that control the device reconfiguration. These are the containers that are actively managed by the Swarmchestrator orchestrator in order to alternate the devices' configuration between the two operational modes, WAN (MBIoT) and LAN (BLE).
4. **Monitoring subsystem** The Swarmchestrator service that will convert the application level metrics to Service Level Agreements (SLOs) which will in turn trigger the application reconfiguration
5. **Cloud Database/Messaging** The cloud based database/messaging service used by the Fuelics platform

Figure 16 System design of the Bi-modal operation of parking space occupancy monitoring IoT devices demonstrator

4.2.2 Metrics for Monitoring and Scaling

Table 4 below enumerates the metric(s) used by this demonstrator application:

Table 4 Demonstrator 2 metrics

Metric name	Description	Influence on scaling/application	Unit
Schedule for short parking restrictions	The time slot when parking space is restricted to a short time, e.g. 09:00-18:00 during weekdays.	During this period the application should use BLE to communicate with the devices. Outside this period it should use NBloT. The change will happen through application reconfiguration by deploying a different set of containers.	time interval

4.2.3 Early prototyping

A summary of the results in early prototyping phase is as follows:

1. The design of the edge device hardware that will host the IoT gateway and allow the configuration and operation of the IoT in bi-modal mode (BLE/NBLoT) has started.
2. The implementation of the services that will be deployed on the edge device is in progress.

4.3 Demonstrator 3 specification

This section presents the system design of the third demonstrator, followed by enumerating the list of identified metrics. Finally, a short status report of the prototype implementation closes this subsection.

4.3.1 Demonstrators System Design

The system architecture consists of multiple **noise sensors** (edge devices), a **remote server**, and two core software components: **data collection** and **noise classification**. Each noise sensor is built on a Raspberry Pi 5, equipped with a noise meter and an omnidirectional microphone. The **data collection** component monitors sound pressure levels (SPL) and forwards short audio clips to the **noise classification** component when predefined thresholds are exceeded. Classification is performed by a CNN-based model, and both SPL data and classification results are stored and visualized via the **remote server**. To address the challenge of deploying Raspberry Pis in public infrastructure—where direct sun exposure can lead to high operating temperatures—**Swarmchestrator** is used to orchestrate classification containers across devices. Its decentralized orchestration allows the system to adapt

dynamically to thermal and computational constraints, ensuring reliable performance in real-world conditions.

Figure 17 Architecture diagram of the noise source classification system

Noise sensor: The edge devices include a Raspberry Pi 5 equipped with a noise meter for measuring sound pressure levels in decibels and an omnidirectional microphone for capturing audio.

Data collection: The data collection component on each noise sensor reads the sound pressure level (SPL) meter and periodically sends SPL data to the database. It also monitors for threshold exceedances. The device continuously captures audio via the omnidirectional microphone, and when the SPL exceeds a predefined threshold, a 10-second segment is forwarded to a noise classification container using k3s service discovery.

Noise classification: The noise classification component is a container orchestrated by Swarmchestrate. It runs a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based on the MobileNetV3 architecture, implemented in PyTorch and trained on the AudioSet dataset. The CNN classifies incoming 10-second audio segments, and the resulting labels are sent to the database.

Remote server: The remote server is a Linux-based VPS running InfluxDB to store SPL measurements and audio classification labels. It also hosts a Grafana instance for data visualization through a monitoring dashboard. Additionally, it acts as the ZeroTier manager node, enabling edge devices to connect within the same VPN.

4.3.2 Metrics for Monitoring and Scaling

In the InnoRenew demonstrator, the noise classification container is managed by Swarmchestrate. Its scaling is driven by the CPU load of edge devices, which reflects the

number of audio recordings submitted for classification—directly influenced by environmental noise and the configured noise threshold. Since the Raspberry Pis are deployed on public infrastructure with varying sun exposure, temperature monitoring is also crucial to prevent thermal throttling. Swarmchestrate uses CPU temperature metrics to schedule containers on cooler devices and shuts down classification containers when device temperatures approach the thermal limit of 95 °C. This ensures continuous operation of the edge network and protects devices from overheating or failure.

4.3.3 Early prototyping

InnoRenew has four functional edge device (raspberry PI + noise sensor) prototypes operating in their lab. The hardware and software setup is functional, but the enclosure design is still being refined to ensure both water resistance and effective thermal dissipation—a combination that presents a complex engineering challenge.

In parallel, InnoRenew is collaborating with the Swarmchestrate team to simulate the system in the SZTAKI partner’s simulation environment, with the goal of assessing scalability to over 100 edge devices and modeling thermal constraints.

```
1  toska_definitions_version: toska_simple_yaml_1_3
2
3  imports:
4  - https://raw.githubusercontent.com/micado-scale/tosca/develop/micado_types.yaml
5
6  repositories:
7  docker_hub: https://hub.docker.com/
8
9  description: ADT for Innorenew audio classification app
10
11 topology_template:
12   node_templates:
13     audio_classification:
14       type: toska.nodes.MICADO.Container.Application.Docker.Deployment
15       properties:
16         image: niki94/audio_classification:latest
17         ports:
18         - port: 42002
19           targetPort: 42002
20           nodePort: 32002
21       requirements:
22         - volume:
23           node: app-configmap
24           relationship:
25             type: toska.relationships.AttachesTo
26             properties:
27               location: /app/configuration.ini
28               subPath: configuration.ini
29
30     app-configmap:
31       type: toska.nodes.MICADO.Container.Config
32       interfaces:
33         Kubernetes:
34           create:
35             inputs:
36               data:
37                 configuration.ini: |
38                 [classification]
39                 model_name=mn40_as
40                 window_size=800
41                 hop_size=320
42
43                 [influx2]
```

Figure 18 ADT snippet of the demonstrator application

Moreover, a cloud-based implementation using the MiCADO [10] orchestrator was successfully deployed and is currently being tested to validate CPU-load scaling rules, which will help streamline the later integration with Swarmchestrate. As part of the deployment,

an Application Description Template (ADT) was prepared to describe the containerized **Noise Classification** component and its scaling behavior. A snippet of the ADT is shown below for illustration.

The setup was deployed on the SZTAKI OpenStack cloud infrastructure, where the MiCADO Master has been installed and configured. The ADT was successfully launched, enabling dynamic orchestration of the **Noise Classification** container. The screenshots below show the created worker nodes, the deployed container and the pods started by MiCADO.

Figure 19 MiCADO dashboard: worker nodes

Figure 20 MiCADO dashboard: audio-classification container

Figure 21 MiCADO dashboard: pods and containers

A test sound sample was received by the deployed application, processed, and the resulting classification label was successfully stored in a remote database.

table	measurement	field	value	_start	_stop	_time	building	sensor_id
8	classification	inference_time_us	387	2025-06-18T08:52:38.000Z	2025-06-18T08:52:45.000Z	2025-06-18T08:52:40.000Z	inoomia	inoomia
1	classification	result	Computer keyboard	2025-06-18T08:52:38.000Z	2025-06-18T08:52:45.000Z	2025-06-18T08:52:40.000Z	inoomia	inoomia

Figure 22 Classification result stored in the InfluxDB

Figure 22 shows the result label “Computer keyboard” and the processing time for the test sound sample.

4.4 Demonstrator 4 specification

This section presents the system design of the fourth demonstrator, followed by enumerating the list of identified metrics. Finally, a short status report of the prototype implementation closes this subsection.

4.4.1 Demonstrators System Design

Solution is serviced by a set of IoT devices that measure environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, pressure. Simultaneously, several Raspberry Pis, acting as an orchestrated IT infrastructure of master and nodes, handles the workload of acquiring, processing and presenting the data from these devices in a distributed manner.

The solution has been designed with three different Use Cases that build the features for the Digital Twin:

- **Data acquisition:** is the part of the solution responsible for gathering the details from every device.
- **Data processing:** is the logic of the solution responsible for preparing the information to an adequate format for the presentation layer.

- **Data Presentation:** is the component of the solution responsible for the visualization of the information retrieved, where the data acquired is presented for the user experience.

The architecture can be represented in a simple manner using C4 model⁴ as in the picture below

Figure 23 Architecture diagram of demonstrator 4

4.4.2 Metrics for Monitoring and Scaling

QoS Expectations

UST’s demonstrator is heavily governed by environmental restrictions, it also relies on a prompt availability of data between devices, hence no long delay on data synchronization should happen during service. Based on these assumptions, an expectation could be around the following figures:

- 7am-7pm running Digital Twin, for up to 50 concurrent users.
- No more than 2 days of data delay on retrieval, preferably UpToDate data.
- No more than one hour delay for processed data.

⁴ <https://c4model.com/>

- No more than 24 hours delay on sync between Digital Twin instances (on Prem and D.R.).

To stick to the expectations above, standard container orchestration metrics such as memory, cpu load and related are taken into account for node-workload -balancing, while other “facility-specific” metrics are used to accomplish the restrictions imposed by energy and bandwidth consumption and availability. The last set of measurements taken into account as part of the orchestration metrics are related to the standard Digital Twin Requirements, such as data pending acquisition or processing, the intensity of the solar light or the battery capacity available. Table 5 demonstrates these metrics.

Table 5 Demonstrator 4 metrics

Group	Metric name	Description	Influence on scaling	Unit	Frequency
Orchestration-related metrics	sun_light_1m	Intensity of the solar light measured every minute	During daylight conditions, regulates the amount of available computing based on the availability to produce solar energy from the solar panels.	W/m ² (e.g., 101.8)	1/min
	battery_level	Capacity of main battery	Combined with the sun_light during daylight conditions, allows to estimate the amount of energy that could be used for "data-processing" tasks. During non-light-hours allows to understand how many of the "data-acquisition" tasks can be achieved. At any time, allows to understand how many "data-presentation" tasks can be executed simultaneously.	Integer (e.g., 250)	1/min
	upload_data_size	Amount of devices pending data delivery	Allows orchestration of "data-acquisition" tasks.	unsigned long (e.g., 258791252254)	1/min
	process_data_size	Size of data files pending processing	Allows orchestration of "data-processing" tasks.	unsigned long (e.g., 258791252254)	1/min
	user_requests	Quantity of users requesting access to the app simultaneously	Allows orchestration of "data-presentation" tasks.	Integer (e.g., 250)	1/min
Other application metrics	dt_incoming_requests_1m	Amount of requests made to the D.T. every minute	Increase above TBD ratio, scales UP number of instances	Integer (e.g., 250)	1/min
	ds_import_1m	Instances of Data Sets for importing received every minute	Allows estimation on the amount of instances that might be required to process the data received	Integer (e.g., 250)	1/min
	kubelet_volume_stats	Data Sets volume size used every minute	Allows estimations of the current usage of specific PVC's defined to store incoming data requests.	unsigned long (e.g., 258791252254)	1/min
	container_cpu_usage_seconds_total	Used to calculate the per-second rate of CPU usage over the last minute	Allows pod horizontal scallation (UP & DOWN) based on requirements	unsigned long (e.g., 258791252254)	1/min
	node_cpu_utilization	Used to understand the node workload	Allows node horizontal scalation (UP & DOWN) based on requirements	unsigned float (e.g., 0.25)	1/min
	pod_cpu_utilization	Used to understand the pod computing workload	Allows pod horizontal scalation (UP & DOWN)	unsigned float (e.g., 0.25)	1/min

4.4.3 Early prototyping

The solution is designed “cloud agnostic” but relies, at this moment of the design phase, following a “cloud agnostic” definition, on an Azure VM instance to service the DR replica of the solution components and is provided, for the demonstration purposes, with the following details:

- Raspberry PI 5: (3 items) 16 GB RAM, 64GB SDCard
- Raspberry PI 2B+: (5 items) 4GB RAM, 64GB SDCard
- Synology NAS ds223: (1 item) 4Tb RAID1 capacity
- 3 X Weather Station arrays with DataLogger.
- 2 x Water Depth sensor for wetland’s depth measurement.
- 1 x Custom built device with sensors for water characterisation measurement.

- 20 x 1Gb ethernet switch for components connectivity.
- 3G/4G connectivity for the IoT devices, as there are heavy restrictions on the extension of any radiofrequency-based connectivity option, which already discards the deployment of any Wi-Fi based approach to connectivity.

At this stage of the design, UST has deployed and configured the physical devices running on a PoC with ansible playbooks, roles and descriptors.

The connectivity to the different IoT environment measurement devices has been tested and has been mocked up (for development purposes) with a NodeRED [11] instance that runs as an IoT device simulator.

Application description files are currently under definition, while a set of container images that resemble the logic expected for the first use case (data acquisition) is in the development phase.

Figure 24 System architecture of demonstrator 4

5. Conclusions

In the Swarmchestrate project, four demonstrators are designed and being implemented in order to validate the Swarmchestrate system integrated by several subsystems such as Orchestration, Ai-based intelligence, Scoring, Knowledge Base, Monitoring, Trust and Security and Digital Twin.

First, a comprehensive questionnaire has been elaborated to collect all characteristics, specialities and requirements of the four demonstrators. This questionnaire addresses different categories of attributes for the applications. Once the questionnaire had been filled in by the four demonstrators, a detailed investigation of the applications was performed.

System design in this document addresses the high-level integration of the different subsystems. Detailed design of the subsystems are introduced in other deliverables of the project. As high-level integration, the project elaborated an overall Swarmchestrate system, where the subsystems are successfully interconnected to provide the necessary functionalities and operations.

During the design of the subsystems and the overall Swarmchestrate system, and as a result of cooperation with the Demonstrators, the detailed design of the four applications has also been elaborated. Both, for the demonstrator applications and for the subsystems and their integration an early prototyping has started.

6. References

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7. Appendix

7.1 Business and technical requirements questionnaire

Demonstrator X

This questionnaire has been designed to collect the requirements of demonstrators from the Swarmchestrate system.

Please complete all the sections as much as possible.

Please do not include any information that you or your organisation considers confidential.

I. Company

Company Overview

Introduce your company in a few paragraphs.

Provide an overview, including its product/service, size, industry, main areas of operation, and so on.

Core Competencies & Expertise

What are the key business & technical strengths of your company (e.g., software development, AI, IoT, cybersecurity, etc.)?

Clients (if applicable)

What types of industries or customers do you serve?

Are there specific application domains relevant to this project?

Relevant Experience in Cloud & Edge Computing

Has your company previously worked with cloud-based applications, containerization, or edge computing? If so, please describe.

Access to Cloud

Does your company have access to cloud resources (public or provider)? If yes, please specify the provider and amount of resources owned.

Motivation for Participating in this Demonstration

Why is your organization interested in this cloud-edge orchestration solution? What key benefits are you hoping to gain or key challenges to address?

Type of Application

Specify the type of your application for example, AI/ML, Web App/Service, IoT, other

II. Use Case Overview

Use Case Motivation and Objectives

Describe the background, motivation, main (high-level) objectives of the use case.

Use Case High-level Architecture

Provide a high-level, conceptual system design, and describe briefly its components.

Current Users

Enumerate users involved and describe user interactions with the systems. (Without technical details or Swarmchestrate.)

If there are different user roles in the system, list them what features or services they can use (e.g., developer, system operator, system user).

Deployment Process

How is the system currently deployed, maintained, and updated?

User Interface

*How do users interact with the system, and how does the system respond?
Provide front-end, GUI screenshot (if applicable, available), as end users (or system operators) will see.*

Technologies, Platforms and Services Used

Which cloud providers, container orchestrators, programming languages, proprietary software, external services or edge devices are currently used?

Is the application cloudified & containerised?

Challenges or Limitations

Are there any constraints, conditions, challenges, or risks that might impact deployment?

III. Swarmchestrate Use Case

Expected Benefits of using Swarmchestrate

What are the added values or benefits that Swarmchestrate promises for the use case implementation?

What KPIs are expected to improve to what extent? What are the baseline values for these KPIs at the beginning of the Swarmchestrate project?

Required Adaptation Efforts

What (process/development/deployment) needs to be changed in your application/system to adapt to the Swarmchestrate implementation paradigm compared to traditional system design, development and operation?

Enumerate the list of “users” of the system, which may include developers and testers (who develop container images/application descriptors) of the application, operator (who deploys and monitors), end users (who use the application).

For each user, specify what they will do, and what competencies are needed (e.g. programming/orchestration concepts/Swarmchestrate system/Kubernetes, domain competence).

IV. Business Model(s)

Is it commercial/open-source development?

Will Swarmchestrate change the business model e.g. pricing model, customer/user engagement, or service delivery?

The business model briefly (pay-per-use, contract for a period, customer).

V. Use Case Requirements

The following subsections collect requirements categorized.

Software Requirements

Enumerate the list of software used by the use case (OS, open source, proprietary software, licences, databases, own developments etc.).

System Requirements

Enumerate hardware (hosts, RAM, CPU, ...) environment(s) required to operate the system.

Indicate preferred clouds (if used).

Enumerate use case-specific devices (e.g., edge devices, sensors, connectivity option).

Data Requirements

Enumerate databases, file storages (cloud storages, etc.) required by the system.

Estimate the amount of data produced/processed/exchanged (if applicable).

Describe briefly where/how these will be stored (maintained, replicated, backed up, ...).

Do you already have cloud storage in a public cloud provider e.g. AWS, Azure, ...?

External Services

Describe if any external services will be used.

Performance Requirements

List the performance criteria required to ensure the minimum (normal) QoS goals (e.g., response times, network bandwidths, CPU speed).

Financial Requirements

How important is cost efficiency/optimisation for the application?

Are there specific cost constraints or considerations?

(e.g., restrictions on spending per workload, preference for certain cloud providers due to cost advantages, etc.)

Security Requirements

Enumerate and explain the security requirements that must be fulfilled to safely operate the system (e.g., encryption, sensitive data, protection of access, VPN, etc.).

QoS Requirements

Are there strict latency requirements?

Energy Consumption Requirements

Are you required to use green/renewable energy for cloud & edge resources?

Do you have energy consumption constraints for Cloud & Edge Resources (e.g. kWh/application or kWh/month)?

Other Requirements

Are there specific geographical constraints for deployment? (e.g., due to data protection). Please specify the Continent, Country, City and GPS if applicable)

Are there any other requirements not fitting to the above categories)?